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Summary report and compilation of design challenges, design briefs and wireframes

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	The GREAT project explores ways of using games-based activities to help citizens express their opinions and attitudes to emerging policies, and making the results available to policy makers. To this end, the task of WP2 is to work with stakeholders on dilemmas related to climate change, carrying out activities to develop design challenges, design briefs and wireframes for games-based activities. This report places this work in context and summarises twelve pilots carried out to inform the design of these activities. The report consists of a summary of the pilots, and a compendium containing the reports from each pilot activity.
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List of Abbreviations

DiBL	Dilemma Based Learning
ECRN	European Creative Rooftop Network
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
UNAL	Universidad Nacional de Colombia
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

D2.1 summarises the work carried out in *WP 2 Intervention Design*. A program of twelve pilots was carried out with users, including external participants with authentic policy concerns, external test users for pilots, and internal pilot participants. The report situates the work carried out from different viewpoints drawn from the literature of co-design and participatory design. It then summarises the pilot activities, draws out the lessons learned, and provides a compendium with detailed documentation of the activities and their outcomes.

The pilots corresponded to the first cycle of project activities, which, as foreseen in the programme of work, is a test cycle. The activity designs that were piloted were effective in creating the desired outcomes: design challenges, design briefs and wireframes. However, as these were pilots, the actual designs created were of less importance than the valuable lessons learned and the capacity building which was achieved. The results were delivered to WP4 and provided the basis for the development of activity designs for steps 1, 2 and 3 of the GREAT case study protocol. Two of the pilots with authentic external users led to case studies which are being taken forward in Cycle 2, in Vienna and in Cyprus.

It has become clear that the possible contexts for interactions in WP2 activities vary greatly. These include various configurations of online and face-to-face for facilitators and participants, as well as the degree to which problem owners have a clear view of the dilemmas which they would like to investigate prior to the start of the case study. This will require customisation of steps 1 and 2 for different problem owners. There is also a need for flexibility in the demarcation between WP2 (responsible for design) and WP3 (responsible for implementation). Pilots of step 3 GREAT have suggested that some design work could be carried out directly with the DiBL back end, and this possibility offers a deeper engagement of stakeholders in the game design process.

1. Introduction

The initial results of WP2 activities fed into the development of the case study cycle (see D4.2), and, in turn, the case study cycle provides the structure within which ongoing WP activities are situated. The body of this deliverable has three sections

Section 2: Perspectives on collaboration in the design of game-based inquiries into policy dilemmas. An examination of different viewpoints on the context within which the design work is carried out and characterisation of the collaborations with stakeholders in terms of the existing literature of co-design and participatory design.

Section 3: Summary of pilot activities. A brief description of each of the activities.

Section 4: Compendium of activities and outcomes. A detailed description of the planning and implementation of each activity.

Readers are expected to read sections 2 and 3 and consult section 4 for more detail if they would like to do so.

The work reported here corresponds to the first three steps of the cycle, shown in Figure 1 below. The activities and outcomes corresponding to these steps are shown in both the facilitator view (i.e. activities to be carried out by the GREAT partners who are leading the case study), and the participant view (i.e. activities and outcomes for the stakeholders in the policy dilemma addressed by the case study).

Figure 1: Steps 1,2 and 3 of the GREAT Case Study Cycle.

2. Perspectives on collaboration in the design of game-based inquiries into policy dilemmas

2.1 The challenges faced by policy-makers

The GREAT project is concerned with the design and evaluation of consultative methods that can support policy-makers in formulating policy. Two of the most significant challenges facing the policy-maker (and particularly so in the area of climate policy) are the complexity of the environment and the achievement of consensus. We now discuss how WP2 relates to these two challenges.

2.1.1 Complexity of the environment

As Lowe et al. have observed, "Researchers have long noted that complexity creates a number of profound challenges for public sector management, particularly in the period since the widespread adoption of New Public Management" (Lowe et al., 2021). This is not simply because the resulting dilemmas are demanding, but rather because they demonstrate the reality of Simon's foundational description of the design challenge of 'bounded rationality' "in situations where the complexity of the environment is immensely greater than the computational powers of the adaptive system." (Simon, 1969 p.166). Policy-makers can respond "either by finding optimum solutions for a simplified world, or by finding satisfactory solutions for a more realistic world". (Simon, 1978, p.350). The thematic focus of GREAT is climate policy, where two immensely complex systems interact: the natural environment and social responses to policy interventions. Faced with this complexity, technocratic solutions addressing an idealised and simplified world are likely to fail when confronted with the reality on the ground.

Lowe and his collaborators have developed a practical framework to support policy makers in dealing with complexity, the 'Human Learning Systems' (HLS) approach to public management. This "... adopts the view that the outcomes public service organizations are commissioned to deliver are not independently produced by those designing interventions or services but from the systems in which they are embedded" (Lowe et al., 2021). Writing within the HLS paradigm, French et al. distinguish four forms of complexity within the policy environment:

1. Compositional complexity, which results from the interdependence and inter-determinant of the causal factors from which outcomes emerge
2. Dynamic complexity, which results from the coevolution of interacting factors and the instability inherent to their environment
3. Experiential complexity, which results from variety, both in the multitude of causal pathways to shared outcomes and in how such outcomes are experienced and valued by individuals
4. Governance complexity, which results from the heterogeneity of actors involved in creating social outcomes, and the absence of a single locus of control for those actors, itself increased by the fragmentation of modern public service landscapes. (French et al., 2021, numbering added).

2.1.2 Meeting the challenge of a complex environment

Responses to the first two of the forms of complexity identified by French et al. (2021) require large scale data collection and analysis in the natural sciences, and which is largely beyond the scope of GREAT. However, the collaborations conducted in WP2 can explore how outcomes are experienced and valued by individuals, and the heterogeneity of actors involved in creating social outcomes, as input to the policy making processes. The ultimate goal is to increase the probability of policies being both socially grounded and environmentally well-informed, and so having a reasonable chance of success. In Simon's terms, policy-makers can use a "heuristic search (selective search using rules of thumb)" to "find decisions that are 'good enough,' that satisfice." (Simon, 1996, p.27). Thus, rather than 'rules of thumb', citizens can be engaged in the process of influencing and/or proposing policies, which can then be evaluated and built on in a stochastic process. 'Stochastic' is understood here in Bateson's sense of "to scatter events in a partially random manner, some of which achieve a preferred outcome" (Bateson, 1988, p.214). In this way, policy options can be trialled and selectively discarded, narrowing down on a set of policies which 'satisfice' the problem at hand, i.e. meet the required impact criteria, without necessarily being optimal. GREAT provides input to this stochastic process, but the evaluation of the impact in practice of the policies which are generated, is beyond the scope of GREAT.

2.1.3 Consensus, agonism and compacts

Social consensus on the climate change emergency has so far been found to be an unreachable goal, and a more realistic ambition may be to achieve a 'compact' which does not require alignment of positions. This approach accepts that stakeholders will not be able to achieve consensus without fundamental changes to their views and values, which may threaten their identity, but proposes that they may be able to achieve a pragmatic division of responsibilities and actions. An example is the initiative for a global compact for refugees, which "sets out practical measures that can be taken by a wide range of stakeholders to enhance international cooperation" (UNHCR, 2016), while an example in the field of climate change is InterAction (2023). This is an agonistic approach, responding to the need identified by Kraff (building on the ideas of Mouffe: "democratic processes must allow for pluralistic views and heterogeneous voices and spaces must exist in which difference, dissent and even conflicts are permitted" (Kraff, 2020). Kraff argues that there must be space for conflicts in public debate, in order to avoid apathy and potentially unmanageable explosions of antagonism, and that this "differs from liberal conceptions of democracy, in which stakeholders are to put aside their own interests in favour of rational negotiation."

In line with this approach, the results of WP2 design processes are designs for games-based activities which provide safe and demarcated spaces, where citizens are invited to express their contrasting views and priorities, and (in the case of DiBL games) explore the relationship between their varied positions. This enables policy-makers to obtain a richer and more accurate picture of citizens' views.

2.2 Support for policy-makers through collaborative design

Given these needs on the part of policy-makers, we now characterise the way that GREAT can contribute to resolving them.

2.2.1 Inclusion: who is included, and how do they benefit

There is a strong tradition of collaborative initiatives with citizens that are fundamentally emancipatory. For example, there is a growing practice of citizen science, which is "reducing the distance between science and society, and contributing to the goal of an inclusive society" (Vohland et al., 2021). Much co-design also takes this emancipatory position, as described by Mosleh and Larsen

Participatory design has historically focused on encouraging ideals of equality... From such an emancipatory perspective, participation can be understood as an ideological and ethical demand for researchers and designers to engage particular groups. (Mosleh & Larsen, 2021)

From this perspective, it would be expected that collaborative design related to climate change policy would involve the widest possible range of stakeholders in formulating policy, with an emphasis on the inclusion of those normally marginalised. Substantial work has been conducted in this line, as summarised by Poderi, G., & Dittrich, Y. (2018). However, the degree to which this work has been successful in empowering citizens to influence policy has been questioned. For example, in a recent paper Chistiansson et al. (2024) conclude that

Our results indicate existing user participation strategies and activities in the public sector and in companies responsible for the development of digital public services. However, these participatory activities maintain input from the general public and users' role as passive and reactive.

Similarly, Palacin et al. (2020) argue that sometimes there is an intent to give an impression of real engagement even when popular control and people's agency are virtually non-existent.

Whatever the success or otherwise of this tradition of inclusive and emancipatory policy design, this is not the approach adopted by GREAT. It is not the purpose nor strategy of the project to involve a wide range of stakeholders in the collaborative design of policy. Rather, our task has two facets, related to the objectives of WP2.

- *Objective 1, To ground project activities in authentic policy dilemmas, in actual challenges of social participation, and in the needs of policy makers.* In addressing this objective, we ensure that project activities and outputs are authentic, in that they address the real needs of policy stakeholders, rather than following the interests of the games industry or of academics. Accordingly, each case study works with a specific policymaker (the dilemma owner) to design interventions and their associated instruments, with additional input from experts and citizens as the policymaker sees fit. By ‘policy-makers’ we refer both to those responsible for deciding on policy measures (e.g. government departments), and those who formulate policy proposals (e.g. NGOs).
- *Objective 2, To produce specifications and design documents which enable WPs 3, 4 & 5 to configure, build, deploy and analyse games that generate data that can inform policy outputs.* In addressing this objective, we seek to collaborate closely with policy stakeholders, to ensure that the detailed designs that are generated enable the interventions and instruments to be implemented in activities with citizens and other stakeholders, and that the results provide insights which contribute to the design of policy.

The distinction drawn between ‘participatory’ and ‘pseudo-participatory’ by Palacin et al. (2020), is relevant here, and informs Table 1 below. However, the term ‘pseudo-participatory’ is inappropriate for GREAT, because the project does not set out to present citizens’ engagement with the designed inquiry as being participatory, except to the extent that they participate in the design of the intervention.

Table 1: Participatory and contributory processes, adapted from Palacin et al. (2020).

	Participatory (design of the GREAT intervention)	Contributory (GREAT intervention deployment and response)
In ... design	Participants shape the artifacts	Participants have no agency to influence design decisions
By ... design	Participants are empowered by the artifact	Participants have a role that is configured by the artifact

2.2.2 Types of experts involved in design activities

While GREAT design activities do not correspond to the emancipatory goals which characterise co-design as a field, they can be understood as co-design in the broad sense used by Sanders and Stappers (2008) "to refer to the creativity of designers and people not trained in design working together in the design development process." In line with this perspective, the principal collaboration in WP2 is with policy stakeholders who are *dilemma owners*, i.e. representatives of organisations of any sort which are (a) confronted by a dilemma in policy formulation or implementation, and (b) have a need to understand the views of other stakeholders and citizens in order to develop a strategy or position in relation to the policy dilemma.

WP2 design activities bring together these policy stakeholders with experts from games industry companies, experts in data management and processing, academics with knowledge of research methods. Together they design games-based inquiries, with the additional inclusion of domain experts as may be required to meet the needs of the policy stakeholders. From this perspective, GREAT design activities may be more accurately described in terms of Participatory Design. Building on the earlier work of Saad-Sulonen, Christiansson et al. (2024) provide a table setting out four types of participation in the design of digital technology:

1. Non-participation
2. Staged participation feedback and testing
3. Staged participation: collaboration
4. Participation as design-in-use.

GREAT WP2 activities in steps 1, 2 and 3 correspond to type 3, characterised by Christiansson et al. as "*Participation informs design, use and context of use. Experts and users collaborate at the specifications level.*" The 'experts' in this case are the policy stakeholders, who have expert knowledge of their own needs and context. The policy stakeholders may also see a need to include other stakeholders in the design of inquiries, and this is encouraged by GREAT. However, this inclusion is not imposed, in order to avoid placing policy stakeholders in a position where they cede control to other stakeholder in the design process, but the product of that process is not acceptable within the constraints of their policy context.

WP2 activities also have aspects of type 4, characterised as "*Participation = design during use, in the context of use. Users design (program, develop, choose, configure, connect) and experts metadesign.*" In step 3, policy stakeholders are invited to participate in selecting and configuring aspects of intervention design based on the specifications, if this is feasible from a technical perspective.

Through the activities of the project as a whole, GREAT engages with an extremely wide range of stakeholders through the activities designed by WP2, once they have been implemented. Indeed, it is the *raison d'être* of the project to explore how games-based activities can be used to this end, and it is the task of WP4 to ensure that this is the case. A rationale of the GREAT is that these players will include vulnerable groups who would be less likely to be reached through traditional media, with a substantial representation of the socially disadvantaged. It may also be expected that many of the people who participate in the games-based inquiries will be living with disabilities, especially for activities delivered through PlanetPlay. In 2019 it was estimated that there were 46.3 million players with disabilities in the United States alone (Cairns et al., 2019), and it appears that they may spend more time playing than other groups of players (Baltzar et al., 2023). There are indications that provision for disabled has improved somewhat, although barriers remain, including in game mechanics and a toxic multiplayer space (Kämäräinen, 2023). Martínez et al. (2024) point out that even when games are not designed for them, gamers with disabilities can find satisfaction in overcoming challenges in an unintended 'hard mode' (without suggesting that this is a satisfactory state of affairs).

WP5 also foresees that a wide range of stakeholders can participate in the design and implementation of the interpretation of case study data and formulation of findings, following a citizen science approach.

2.2.3 Empowerment of policy-makers

Lodato and Di Salvo (2018), drawing on Huybrechts, Bensech and Geib (2017), argue that for participatory design (PD) "institutional frames are extant power installed in bureaucratic forms, whether an institution is liberatory or oppressive. For PD to meet its political objectives, these frames must be leveraged or challenged." From this perspective, it may seem counter-intuitive that GREAT seeks to empower policy-makers, who by virtue of their ability to influence policy are already in positions of power or influence within institutional structures. However, on the principle of not letting the best be the enemy of the good, GREAT focuses on supporting policy-makers of all types in producing better policy outcomes, by providing them with information about the social context. This involves the 'empowerment' of policy-makers, not in the sense of increasing their power vis a vis citizens, but rather in enabling them to engage in the design of the instruments and interventions, which in turn generate the information about the social context that is an essential input to informed policymaking processes.

The benefits of engaging policy-makers with the collaborative formulation of intervention designs are not limited to the gathering of information. From a realist evaluation perspective, all policy interventions are applied in a particular context and

interact with mechanisms to produce outcomes. Ray Pawson, in his valedictory “The Science of Evaluation, A Realist Manifesto”, concludes that there is a need for middle-range research programmes to be organised to examine intervention theories, probing their applicability and where they hold good. (Pawson, 2013, p. 128). Within the literature of Co-Design, this aligns with the focus on theories of change, which articulate the intervention logic of a project and the steps necessary to achieve a desired goal or impact. (Drabble et al., 2021). However, this is not easy to achieve when “the wider ecosystem that an intervention will be working within remains largely unknown” (Drabble et al., 2021). The work of WP2 makes a contribution to addressing this problem (although by no means eliminates it), by enabling policy-makers to design consultative activities which articulate in some way their (possibly unexamined) theory of change, and then implement those activities to generate feedback concerning their assumptions on citizen’s views and likely responses to interventions.

2.2.4 Bootstrapping the GREAT methodology

In its intervention designs, GREAT works with authentic policy stakeholders to address real-world policy dilemmas. The external stakeholders who collaborate in the project in these activities typically work under pressure to resolve pressing problems with practical consequences for citizens and societies. Before undertaking case studies with these stakeholders, it is essential that GREAT is confident that the methodology is well articulated, that the case study leaders and facilitators clearly understand their roles, and that the proposed activities will be effective. To this end a Case Study Protocol has been developed in WP4 which articulates the steps to be carried out in implementing a case study. In the first year of the project, however, this protocol was under development. Consequently, WP2 was confronted by a bootstrapping problem, being tasked to carry out activities within a methodology which had not yet been fully defined. As a result, the activities reported here constitute the basis of a design dialogue between WP2 and WP4, in which the activities of WP2, on the one hand contributed to the development of the protocol and on the other hand were informed by the shared emerging understanding of the steps of the cycle which was emerging in the shared work of the project partners. The results of WP2 activities fed into the development of activity designs for the GREAT case study protocol in WP4, providing example activity processes which the facilitators of steps 1, 2 and 3 can follow, or use as inspiration. It is planned to update and extend these activity designs following successive iterations of WP2 activities.

Accordingly, the activities reported here are pilots which meet the design needs of the pilot cycle of the project. Work with stakeholders in the full case studies addressing authentic policy dilemmas is underway at the time of writing and will be reported in D2.2.

2.3 Methodology

The methodology for WP2 activities is established, in broad terms, by the overall case study methodology set out in D4.1. At the other end of the scale, a detailed methodology is established for WP2 activities with each stakeholder, documented in section 4 of this document. Within this context, in this section we add information about some common methodological aspects in WP2 design activities.

2.3.1 Use of toolkits and prototypes

Our co-design activities with policy stakeholders can be seen in terms of Sanders and Stappers' distinction between probes, toolkits and prototypes, which they describe as follows.

- Probes: "materials that have been designed to provoke or elicit response. For example, a postcard without a message.
- Toolkits "(made up of a variety of components) are specifically confirmed for each project/domain. People use the toolkit components to make artefacts about or for the future.
- Prototypes; "physical manifestations of ideas or concepts. They range from rough (giving the overall idea only) to finished (resembling the actual end result)."

Sanders and Stappers (2014)

Of these, intervention design activities in WP2 primarily involve toolkits and prototypes. Probes are less relevant, because the policymaker participants will be strongly engaged in the dilemma by virtue of their responsibility for resolving it, and it is not desirable to guide their responses by exposing them to probes selected by the project team.

Building on the ideas of Susan Leigh Star, Lodato and Di Salvo state that "Infrastructuring can be broadly described as the construction or co-construction of sociomaterial resources for participation." (Lodato and Di Salvo, 2018) They describe how designers provide resources for ongoing engagement, constructing worksheets and games and convening workshops, which gather together diverse actors to collaboratively explore an issue and its consequences. Within the co-design tradition physical infrastructure predominates. Lodato and Di Salvo (2018) point out that "Aside from classic generic tools like pencil, paper and sticky notes, there is a growing number of tailored tools specifically designed to support ideation", mentioning IDEO's Methods Cards (IDEO 2015), Dan Lockton's Design with Intent Toolkit (Lockton 2017) and the LEGO Serious Play kits (McKusker, 2020) among others. However, there is no reason why infrastructure should have to be physical, and indeed Star's original conception of infrastructuring was developed in the context of ICT and the Internet. As befits a

project focused on digital games, in its toolkits GREAT makes use of both physical and virtual resources. Thus, face-to-face activities may make use of flipcharts, post-its, marker pens, etc., and also online tools such as presentation software and digital whiteboards (e.g. Google Jammer and Miro). Remote collaborations can be supported by a combination of digital whiteboards, social media, presentation software, email, video conferencing, etc.

The emphasis on the physicality of tools in co-design is reflected in Sanders and Stappers' statement that "Prototypes are physical manifestations of ideas or concepts." Sanders and Stappers (2014). In GREAT, while physical prototypes are not ruled out, the simplest approach is to work on virtual prototypes which reflect the environment for which the design is intended. Be this as it may, Sanders and Stappers describe how prototype can play a number of important roles, including their capacity to "confront theories, because instantiating one typically forces those involved to consider several overlapping perspectives/theories/frames" and to "confront the world, because the theory is not hidden in abstraction." Sanders and Stappers (2014). In GREAT these capacities are realised through the work on concrete designs to inquire into real world problems through specific methods.

2.3.2 Participants in the activities

In alignment with the need for pilots, the workplan (section 1.2.3) foresaw that participants in Cycle 1 could be internal test users. Nevertheless, opportunities emerged during Cycle 1 activities to work with external groups who were willing to collaborate in the development of the case study cycle and methodology. These included both test users and stakeholders with authentic policy challenges such as the Die Grünen in Frankfurt, and the Urban Gorillas NGO in Cyprus. The project made use of these opportunities as they arose, in order to maximise the value of the outcomes in the development of the case study cycle and protocols, and the participants in the activities reported here were a mix of internal test users, external test users, and external dilemma owners.

As work progressed it became clear that the stakeholders who would participate in WP2 activities would vary greatly. In addition to the social and cultural characteristics which may be expected to differ in the wide range of contexts in which the GREAT project is active, problem owners and stakeholders participating in activities vary greatly in their knowledge and expertise and in the amount of time that they can dedicate to GREAT activities. The activities reported here reflect this range of types of participation.

The pilots reported here followed the overall ethical approval for the GREAT project, which was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the coordinating partner, DIPF. This establishes requirements which apply to all the research carried out in the

project and provides templates for briefing participants and for informed consent. Additionally, each partner conforms to the requirements of their own institution, which may apply additional constraints or requirements. The leaders of case studies carried out in the European Union and the UK apply for ethical approval in their own institute. Case studies outside the European Union, for example associate partners based in South Africa and China, are processed through the Research Ethics Committee of the coordinating partner, DIPF.

2.3.3 A standard format for representing plans and results

In order to draw coherent conclusions from GREAT case studies it is essential that the intentions and plans of the coordinators, the activities carried out, and the outcomes achieved are clearly documented. To this end a template was developed for WP2 activities, covering planning (to be completed prior to carrying out the activity) and results (to be completed following completion of the activity). The activities reported in the compendium below are all documented using this template. WP4 has included the template in the GREAT case study protocols and extended its application to all steps in the cycle.

In completing this documentation, the leaders of the case study and the facilitators of the design process need to make decisions on a number of aspects of the design process, as shown in figure 2 below

Figure 2: Questions for facilitators of the design process.

3. Summary of pilots for steps 1, 2 and 3

The compendium below details 12 activities carried out by 6 different partners in 7 different contexts. There were 66 participants in the activities, of whom 34 were female (F) and 32 were male (M). Two collaborations were established with authentic partners such as those to be involved in GREAT cycles from 2 onwards, i.e. organisations which are confronted by real and immediate policy dilemmas. These

authentic partners were Die Grünen in Frankfurt, Germany, and Urban Gorillas in Cyprus. UNAL university in Colombia provided external pilot users for two activities, while DIPF, UB and ZSI provide internal pilot users. Most of the pilots made use of digital tools, with only two using physical tools. However, there was a wider range of modalities, with 2 face-to-face, 4 mixed, and 6 remote.

Table 2, below provides an overview of the key features of the pilots carried out.

Table 2: Pilot interventions conducted.

Step	Lead partner	Context	Location	Number participants (M/F)	Authentic stakeholder s involved	Tools (physical/ digital)	Modality (F2F, mixed, remote)
1	ZSI	Die Grünen	Frankfurt, Germany, and online	9 (4F / 5M)	5 policy-makers (Green Party). 4 concerned citizens	Physical and digital	Mixed
1	UNIR	Universidad Nacional de Colombia UNAL	Colombia and online	8 (3F /5M)	0	Digital	Remote
1	UB	UB internal pilot	Bolton, UK	18 (10F / 8M)	0	Physical	F2F
1	DIPF	DIPF internal pilot	Frankfurt, Germany.	5 (1F / 4F)	0	Digital	F2F
1	FU	Urban Gorillas	Cyprus	1 (1F)	1 policy maker	Digital	Remote
2	ZSI	Die Grünen	Frankfurt, Germany	4 (2F / 2M)	3 Policy makers (Green Party), 1 concerned citizen	Digital	Mixed
2	UNIR	UNAL	Colombia and online	8 (3F / 5M)	0	Digital	Remote
2	SGI	Internal design brief pilot	Online	6 (4F 2M)	0	Digital	Remote
2	FU	Urban Gorillas	Cyprus	2 (2F)	2 policy-makers	Digital	Mixed
3	ZSI	Vienna dilemma design	Vienna, Austria, and online	3 (3F)	3 policy-makers	Digital	Mixed
3	SGI	Internal wireframe pilot	Online	6 (4F 2M)	0	Digital	Remote
3	SGI	Internal wireframe pilot	Online	6 (4F 2M)	0	Digital	Remote
3	FU	Urban Gorillas	Cyprus	2 (2F)	2 policy-makers	Digital	Remote2

3.1 Step 1: Create and prioritise research topics

In the Case Study Protocol, step 1 of the case study cycle is described as a workshop activity which determines what the case study will achieve, and with whom. In such a workshop, GREAT collaborates with a problem owner, i.e. a stakeholder organisation (or group of stakeholders) that has agreed to partner with the project to carry out a case study. The outcomes of this work will identify:

- The most relevant current dilemmas faced by the problem owner.
- The insight and evidence the problem owner would like to obtain about citizens' attitudes and preferences.
- Indicators, i.e. decisions, choices or behaviours which would indicate citizens attitudes and preferences.
- The groups of citizens and organisations who should be involved if the problem owner is to obtain accurate and representative information.

In addition to the expected variation in participants discussed in 2.3 above, it became clear that an additional consideration pertains for step 1. The list of outcomes detailed in the bullet list above assumes that the problem owner is aware of the need to obtain input to the policy decision making from citizens, but has not yet articulated a focus or the way in which this should be done. In practice this may be the case for the problem owner, or it may be that they already know exactly which issues they want to address, or they may find themselves at any point in between. As a result, the design of step 1 activities has to adapt to a range of different situations. This becomes less true in step 2, where participants are discussing the design of interventions which they will in all probability not previously have considered, and largely vanishes as a factor for subsequent steps.

Pilot 1.1 Die Grünen, Frankfurt

Within a month of the start of GREAT, contacts were established with Die Grünen (the Green Party) in Frankfurt with a view to collaborating in pilots, and potentially a case study.

The workshop methodology worked well overall. The pilot was conducted with 9 politicians and campaigners who already knew each other, which is a typical scenario for a GREAT case study. Video conferencing was used to connect the project facilitators (together in a room in Vienna) with the participants (together in a room in Frankfurt). The supporting tools were Zoom and Miro whiteboard software. This is well established software, and most people had worked with similar applications before

except one older participant. It had been hoped that it would be possible to discuss the top two ranked topics:

- Traffic and mobility, priority for cycle lanes etc.
- Housing, how to make it affordable, how to continue building without using up all the green spaces

However, time did not allow for it. Indeed, lack of time was a common concern in nearly all the pilot activities. The participants were strongly aligned with the GREAT approach, there was enough interest to continue, which led to a next workshop. However, timing was already a big issue and getting various people together for a follow-up was challenging.

Pilot 1.2 Colombia

This workshop was the first of two with the same participants, involving members of staff and students from Universidad Nacional de Colombia (UNAL). It was highly structured around the required outputs for Step 1, using strongly facilitated brainstorming and voting to expedite the process. Like pilot 1.1, the workshop was carried out entirely by means of videoconferencing, with participants who were not known to the facilitators. However, unlike 1.1, all the participants and facilitators were in separate locations.

Zoom was used in combination with Google Jamboard (whiteboard software) and Mentimeter (voting software, free version), which proved to be an effective collection of tools. There was a glitch in the use of Mentimeter, as the facilitators did not realise that the participants were required to move on to the next question before it became visible. It also became clear that it is necessary to leave plenty of space for contributions on Jamboard, with a separate page for each question, as can be seen from the screenshots in the Compendium below. To make this work well, the outcomes from the previous page need to be transferred to the subsequent page. This task, and the creation of voting options on the fly as the discussion progresses, both mean that the facilitation team needs a member who is dedicated to managing the tools and updating them.

All the planned outputs were generated:

- Desertification by cattle and agribusiness.
- Tax to regulate agricultural activity.
- Range of options for who to collect information from.

Prior to the session the facilitators were concerned that there would not be sufficient opportunities to create confidence among online participants and to generate

discussion. In the event, there was a substantial number of interventions by participants. However, this discussion was largely between the facilitator and the participants, and there was little spontaneous discussion between participants.

Pilot 1.3 UB internal pilot.

This pilot was also highly structured, but the approach taken was very different from pilot 1.2. It was also face-to-face rather than online, and was based on tightly-timed iterations of break-out discussions in small groups, followed by plenary discussion and decision making. A large interactive white board and a conventional flip chart were used as a focus for discussion and to record the outcomes. This process enabled a large number of policy dilemmas to be identified in a relatively short period of time. The outcomes addressed only the first aspect of the design challenge, i.e. “policy dilemma to be addressed in the case study”, and there remained a need to select one of the two long-term priorities identified (policies for population control and for government sanctions to reduce emissions). In a full case study there would be a need to repeat or supplement this activity in order to address all the outcomes of Step 1. However, given that the activity took only an hour, the method was an effective and compressed activity design for a structured face-to-face brainstorm, and it was developed into an exemplar activity design in WP4.

Pilot 1.4 DIPF internal pilot

This pilot was conceived in response to the problem of time pressure faced in pilots 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3. It is intended for a situation where the participants from a problem owner are under severe time pressure, and have very limited opportunity to meet together. In this design, the project can offer them support by interviewing the participants individually, documenting their positions, and preparing for a plenary meeting which can concentrate on decision making and reach a resolution in a relatively short period of time. Five interviews were carried out, four face-to-face interviews and one remote. This was followed by a face-to-face plenary meeting at which participants gave brief pitches, and immediately entered into substantive discussion. Within an hour, the group had finished discussing issues around the five questions and provided detailed ideas, elaborations and answers, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach when working with participants who have low availability for meetings. The group agreed that car-dependency was the policy dilemma that needed to be addressed. Specifically, they wanted to know if their city could be made less reliant on private car use and more on public or green transportation. The stakeholders to be engaged as informants were families, young or single people. The effectiveness of this approach was very encouraging, but it is to be expected that more time would be required in the plenary discussion in a high stakes environment, where policy decisions with real-world consequences are to be decided.

Nevertheless, the procedure provides a shortcut to a substantive discussion, and a valuable resource for the organiser of a GREAT case study.

Pilot 1.5 Urban Gorillas

Towards the end of Cycle 1, collaboration was established with Urban Gorillas (<https://urbangorillas.org/>), a small NGO which has carried out ecological interventions in municipalities across Cyprus. Like Die Grünen in Frankfurt, these are an authentic partner, but unlike Die Grünen they also had a clear and unmet existing policy challenge that they urgently wished to investigate: the desire to make use of rooftop spaces in the fight against climate change, and the dilemmas of conflicting interests which this generates. They therefore have a pre-existing environmental mission, and have thought extensively about the kinds of initiatives which they would like to support. There was therefore no need for a workshop to brainstorm or elaborate ideas.

This clarity, and the small size of the organisation meant that it was possible to carry out step 1 with only one participant, a board member of Urban Gorillas. The activity consisted of two remote conversations of one hour each, between the facilitator and a board member of the NGO. The first conversation presented the GREAT project, and established interest in participation, and the second discussed possible themes which could serve as the basis of a dilemma game in Nicosia. The outcome was to focus on the use of roof spaces to combat climate change, with three possible strategies:

- Use of public/large buildings roof spaces as social spaces
- Greening of multiple private owned buildings roof spaces
- Water management/collection on private owned buildings roof spaces

Decision on which aspect was deferred for the Step 2 activity, as was the identification of stakeholder respondents.

This pilot showed that it is both necessary and possible to adapt the GREAT case study cycle to circumstances where the dilemma owner has no need for a workshop activity to identify their policy dilemma priorities. Nevertheless, the activity was not unstructured, as the facilitator's interactions were informed by both the required outcomes for step 1, and of the practical outcomes needed to move forward with a games-based intervention.

3.2 Step 2: Collaborate in study design

Step 2 builds on the design briefs developed in step 1 to determine what the game-based activities will achieve and how. Facilitators collaborate with stakeholders to define:

- Specific dilemmas requiring information on citizens' preferences and attitudes which are of importance to the problem owner.
- The expected insight and evidence that can be offered to policy makers.
- The specific user groups who will be involved and their roles.
- How data will be gathered, analysed and delivered to stakeholders

These outcomes constitute a design challenge, to be addressed in Step 3.

Pilot 2.1 Die Grünen, Frankfurt

In this pilot the participants (the same as for pilot 1.1) were authentic, in the sense of being politicians and campaigners, and they were strongly in favour of the citizen engagement proposed by GREAT. Nevertheless, it became clear in both pilots 1.1. and 2.1 that the policy stakeholders did not have an immediate need for the proposed GREAT activities in terms of a specific dilemma experienced by a specific organisation or group. Rather, they participated because of a personnel invitation, and a desire to support the project. Because there was no real commitment, a lot of discussion concerned a process for better engagement and communication (in both directions) with people who have different expectations, who do not know how politics and administration is done, and who don't get engaged until they are personally affected, even if their participation is invited. This is particularly true of people who are not engaged, marginalised people who do not have interest groups representing them, young people, parents, etc. Similarly, many participants identified a lack of information for citizens about what has been decided and implemented, and awareness of the processes. These views strongly validated the approach taken by GREAT. Indeed, the greatest interest among participants was for a game-based inquiry into how citizen participation could be fostered in the face of widespread unwillingness to engage in political processes.

The practical outcomes of the workshop were:

- The participants gained a detailed understanding of what the GREAT games look like and what kind of functionalities they have.
- A decision that the participants would look for further possibilities to implement a real-case scenario in Frankfurt.

The pilot indicated that the development of a personal or professional commitment to GREAT and to a specific case study is important in creating a strong collaboration with stakeholders, and it should not be left to chance. This is made more challenging by the participants' limited availability and time, when compared with the substantial effort required in the design and implementation of the games.

Accordingly, the ZSI-research team concluded that in order to implement a real-life case study, and specifically to carry out activities for steps 1, 2 and 3, it is not sufficient to find authentic participants who are willing to come to a few meetings. Rather, the GREAT team needs to work with policy stakeholders with an urgent need for game-based approaches (DiBL dilemma games) and consultation with the wider gamer community (Playmob platform). Policy makers have only limited time and availability but if GREAT activities can be aligned with political goals, they may be able to obtain additional funding for staff and resources. If the timing and urgency is tight, GREAT can help resolve policy-makers difficulties by upgrading the typical use of less engaging, with more interactive and gamy formats like MentiMeter, Slidos, Kahoot, Curioid, Wooclap or similar. A particular need is for support for non-professional participation. It was noted that GREAT staff are paid for their time, and that full time politicians can justify participation as part of their professional activities, but campaigners, students and other citizens have no support for their participation. In the Frankfurt pilot, the student representatives seemed willing to continue the collaboration, but some compensation (even if only for out of pocket expenses) would generate greater commitment.

Pilot 2.2 UNAL Colombia

This pilot involved the same participants as 1.2. As in other pilots, the time was very short for carrying out all the necessary activities, but some campaigners, politicians, etc. may have still less time available, depending on institutional buy-in and organisational resource allocation. Finding creative solutions to make effective use of limited time with stakeholders will be one of the key success factors for the GREAT cycles. It is proposed to add preparatory activities to identify policies or proposed policies that require information. These could involve one-to-one interviews, as in pilot 1.4, perhaps with junior personnel from stakeholder organisations. In any event, this is a consideration to be addressed by all case study coordinators.

In this pilot, we chose a strongly directed method, and this proved effective in generating the required outcomes and articulating the process. Indeed, more direction might increase effectiveness still further. However, the high degree of direction also constrains the spontaneity of dialogue, and may also constrains the range of ideas generated. Moreover, it remains to be seen how stakeholders with a high degree of public or social responsibility will respond to a highly directed process. Consequently, the ground rules for the meetings will need to be agreed with participants at the beginning of each case study.

Despite four participants dropping out (including one of the principal contributors from session 1) participation was maintained throughout the two sessions, and indeed gathered momentum.

It was harder than expected to explain to participants what they needed to do. The facilitation team agreed that:

- The interaction between administrators and administered, or between governed and governors, should be stressed still more strongly at the beginning of the session.
- The facilitators encouraged the participants to think of designing a scenario as they might create the outline of a drama or TV series episode, with a cast, a setting and key events in the plot. It was agreed that this helped the participants to understand what was being asked of them. This was a piece of improvised guidance during the session, but should be incorporated as a resource for facilitators.

As in Pilot 1.2, there was a satisfactory degree of interaction between participants and the facilitator, but an almost complete absence of horizontal interactions between participants. Consequently the sessions took on something of the nature of a taught class, with participants responding to prompts. This may not occur in an authentic environment in future cycles, but it is a design criteria which should be addressed. In response to the lack of horizontal discussion, the facilitators found that they were speaking more than they had planned to, providing reflections which could more effectively have come from the participants.

Conversation also tended to be dominated by a small number of participants, and this was hard to correct online. Future designs should set out to avoid this, perhaps through the use of break-out activities, or through collaboration with facilitators who know the participants and can make targeted interventions to include them all. Similarly, Jamboard was an effective tool, but it is possible that the use of post-its took the place of dialogue. It would be a high risk strategy to organise an online workshop without this type of support, but this trade-off should be borne in mind when designing future sessions.

Pilot 2.3 internal design pilot

This workshop took place in the second of three training sessions provided by SGI for project partners. The first training session, which is not detailed in this report, consisted of an introduction to the DiBL platform, while the second session corresponded to Pilot 2.3. This involved conceiving a design that would provide the basis for a dilemma game. It was intended both to raise capacity in the project, and establish a practical design method.

When work starts on designing a dilemma, there is often no clear statement of exactly what is to be examined, what outcomes are needed, and how to tell the story. The focus of this session was to pilot a worksheet, based on prior work by SGI in the field

of education. The pilot investigated how an adapted application of this instrument can guide this process in the different context of citizen engagement in policy. It is intended to further develop this method so that it is more encompassing and rigorous.

The participants were highly engaged and worked without difficulty with the worksheet and the Miro board. They experienced a steep learning curve on how to make a good dilemma, and agreed that it is not easy to design a good dilemma that actually gets people discussing what you want them to discuss in a way that you want them to discuss it. However, they were very productive.

The outputs of the workshop, and subsequent work on pilots by FU and ZSI demonstrate that they are competent in identifying dilemmas and understanding what is possible within the technical framework, as well as thinking through how we can get people to engage with the themes we want. These are essential competencies for the implementation of case studies with authentic problem owners.

It was shown that the dilemma design worksheet is an effective tool for defining dilemmas in the context of GREAT, and it is recommended to include it in an activity design in the GREAT protocol.

Pilot 2.4 Urban Gorillas, Cyprus

This pilot was built on Pilot 1.5, and enriched by the work in Pilot 2.3 with the authentic participation of Urban Gorillas (UG). The activity was led by FU, with the participation of two members of UG, the board member from Pilot 1.5, with the addition of a project manager (and also board member) and an urban planner with expertise on the subject of rooftop spaces, the theme identified in the Step 1 activity.

The practical outcome of the meeting was to refine the dilemma regarding roof spaces to concentrate on the greening of privately multi owned rooftops and the incentives that could be offered to citizens. Urban Gorillas would like to test this policy with two specific groups in Nicosia: firstly architects, planners, designers and engineers, and secondly building owners, contractors and developers.

UG explained the concept of rooftop greening and how the repurposing of rooftops can work towards climate neutrality, and identified the specific policy relating to rooftops and the overall concepts to be tested. Specific groups of participants were identified (citizens/building owners etc), as well as the potential use of the results and the desired outcomes for UG. Thus, the target outcomes were met in a very effective and time efficient manner, building on the existing focus of the NGO and working with experts in the target field, who had already thought deeply about the dimensions of their chosen dilemma.

During the meeting the participants had access to DiBL, and to the expertise of the facilitator who had participated in GREAT training in DiBL. This was valuable in giving the participants a clear understanding of how the game would work.

A shared Google document was created which included materials which could be exploited in the design of a DiBL game.

The shared document on Google Drive recorded:

- Lists of Incentives for rooftop repurposing.
- A list of resources to support policy development.
- List of Good Practices and Case Studies.
- Identification of Barriers to Rooftop usage.

Multiple potential groups were identified for participation in the DiBL game:

- Homeowners.
- Building Developers.
- Management companies.
- Architects.
- People who rent accommodation.
- Neighbours.
- Potential buyers.

An important next step moving forward with the DiBL pilot is to move from categories of participants to actual participant groups who would be willing to engage in the game.

3.3 Step 3: Collaborate in game design

This step concerns design of interaction and interface in the games-based activities, linking the design ideas of stakeholders with the project technical team, as regards:

- Gameplay interaction design.
- Interface design.
- Content selection and design.

The wireframes which emerge from this process are passed to WP3 for implementation and delivery.

Pilot 3.1 Vienna dilemma game design (ZSI)

The Frankfurt pilot case study provided the information needed a design brief in step 2. Unfortunately, the respondents were not available for further activities and the process came to a halt. In parallel, the ZSI team had the ambition to design a dilemma

game, based on a real dilemma in Vienna, which addressed a similar issue to the one discussed in the Frankfurt case. This activity therefore combined the outcomes already achieved in Frankfurt, which would otherwise have remained unused, while preparing an exemplar for a possible future case study in Vienna.

This pilot explored the design of a DiBL game, based on the input received from the workshops in Steps 1 and 2, exploring how easy or difficult it would be for someone with little or no experience of the platform to co-design a dilemma game. The three participants from ZSI originally planned to design the game on their own, using the knowledge one of the team had gained in the training they had received on DiBL.

Only a small number of people were involved, so the activity was unstructured, with focus provided by the objectives and materials available. The pilot lasted approximately 2 hours of work in the ZSI team, 3 hours of the ZSI and SGI teams together, and a day by the SGI team in creating the template. It proved quite difficult to formulate the game logic which would translate the identified dilemma into a game with various options that would trigger people's opinions. When the design process became blocked, partner SGI were contacted, and they talked through the storyline. SGI then made a draft design for the game, and it was discussed again with additional changes made by SGI.

The game will not be deployed as it stands, but the insight into how such DiBL games can be designed and the template that was created by SGI will be taken forward in developing the Vienna case study.

It was learned that:

- It is not a simple task to transfer a question or dilemma into a serious game logic. It is a substantial challenge to involve people in this activity (be they facilitators or stakeholders) if they are not experienced in game design, and it takes time to learn the logic of DiBL, and experience is needed to assess how long a game would take. It was very important to get the help from a professional to transfer the story into a coherent dilemma game. Accordingly, it is suggested that any co-design activities with stakeholders should only be carried out with a very limited number of people. An alternative approach is for the DiBL team to make a first draft in collaboration with pilot facilitators, based on the input from the stakeholders. This can then be presented to the stakeholders and modified subject to their further input.
- It became clear that it is important to establish where and how we can get data for WP5 impact assessment once the game is implemented. This has to be thought through from the very beginning, e.g.

- Will the players have discussions in a face-to-face setting and can we document that?
 - Will the game be entirely online, and what data can we collect?
 - How and when should we split up the groups into breakout rooms?
 - How do we phrase the questions to make sure we get answers that are relevant for the policy stakeholders?
 - Do we rather let the plays take on certain roles (role play) or do we want them to voice their own opinions directly?
 - How will we make the game engaging?
- Miro works well for this type of design activity. Miro templates which can be implemented in DiBL games would be very useful, providing designers with a set of templates they could choose from and adapt to their specific context and needs. The Miro design created in this pilot could be adapted as a template.

Pilot 3.2 Internal design pilot

This pilot took place during the second and third of three training sessions organised by partner SGI to raise capacity in the consortium, with the participation of six project staff from five institutions. The participants worked in teams to develop wireframes and draft DiBL games, picking up on some of the ideas generated in pilots of steps 1 and 2. The purpose of pilot 3.2 was to explore the boundaries and trade-offs that exist between the use of Miro to create wireframes, and directly creating draft games on the DiBL platform.

The evaluation and the experience of working with the participants suggests two possible roles for GREAT case study facilitators:

1. GREAT staff facilitate the wireframe design of a DiBL game on Miro (or something similar), and then pass that over to SGI for detailed technical implementation, following the procedure proposed in the description of work.
2. GREAT case study facilitators learn to use the DiBL back end, and create dilemma games themselves, with support from SGI as required. This process appears daunting at first, but the participants were very effective in their use of the DiBL platform. In the evaluation session they said they enjoyed the technical work, designing the pages and linking to questions.

The evidence from this and other pilots shows that (1) is a viable strategy, but that (2) is also feasible, and may offer stronger and more agile feedback from the stakeholders, because of facilitators well-established communication links with the stakeholders. It is suggested that each university partner should have access to a DiBL tenant which they can experiment with, with support from SGI where necessary.

In future workshops with stakeholders, a slightly larger group might be better if possible, to help keep the interactions flowing. More time should be allocated for design activities on the DiBL platform, as participants were keen to continue, but only managed to do one step into the dilemma. This precluded branching, which is complex and involves key design decisions: When should players make a choice? What happens with that choice afterwards? What dilemmas?

Evaluation was carried out and details are in the compendium item Pilot 3.2. The feedback was positive, with no aspects rated as 'stop'. The most significant issue raised concerned implementation of a participant pre-survey in DiBL, for gathering initial input and opinions from citizens to inform the way that the dilemmas are dealt with. This reflects the need to adapt the use of DiBL in GREAT, which concerns citizen consultation rather than learning. There were also requests for templates, and suggestions made for design support functionality.

Pilot 3.3 Urban Gorillas

The dilemma and the outline for the game had been identified in activities with two of the leading participants in Urban Gorillas in Cyprus. The dilemma game design was created by the pilot coordinator, and a member of the SGI technical team, who acted in what may be termed a 'consulting' role, in the sense that they had gathered requirements from the UG team, and then took responsibility for the design.

The activity consisted of a dialogue between the pilot facilitator (who had developed a good understanding of the dilemma and the objectives of the sponsor, and also had a good understanding of the DiBL platform) and a member of the SGI team (who could guide the facilitator through the detail of the design process, and provide guidance on effective designs).

Prior work with UG had developed a clear and authentic question: What incentives would be effective in promoting an initiative for the greening of privately multi owned rooftops? For this particular DiBL game a minimum of 8 participants are necessary, with a maximum of 50.

The SGI representative stressed the need to find ludic activities, so that the activity does not become simply a matter of "Well if you give me money I will do it". Similarly, climate change should not be introduced too early, as when climate change is mentioned it distracts from the focus of the participant on the dimensions of the scenario.

An option was to work with current apartment owners and to ask questions about how they would feel about using the roofs and gain instinctive feedback. The proposal of

an incentive could then be introduced, and roles distributed. Issues which arise include:

- One person lives on the top floor, but another lives on the ground floor that already has a private garden: should the incentives be the same?
- Should access be allowed for all residents, even if they don't agree with the initiative? Would a tax reduction be an effective measure?

The game concentrates on new buildings, and target groups were identified: apartment owners and/or developers (the construction company who build and sell). The game should include role play aspects, for example types of owners – family – single – older couple etc. as well as for residents who live in different parts of the building. A questionnaire should be added at the end, to gather further ideas from the participants. The fact that the facilitator of the pilot had completed training in DiBL had greatly helped in the gathering of relevant information, and also meant that the development of the wireframes proceeded rapidly. The expert advice from the SGI staff member was invaluable in guiding the game design strategy.

4. Conclusions

The work reported in this deliverable directly addresses Objective 1 of the GREAT project: *Establish ways in which games can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy-makers.* The activities which are described are pathfinder interventions which provide a solid foundation for implementation of GREAT activities corresponding to steps 1, 2 and 3 of the case study cycle in subsequent case studies with authentic problem owners. In those future case studies, the design work of WP2 which builds on this deliverable will be of central importance to the project. When implemented with a wide range of stakeholders and citizens the games-based activities will generate the data necessary to address Objective 2. *Understand the actual and potential impact that games can have on citizens' engagement in social issues and challenges, and on policy stakeholders' awareness of citizens' attitudes and preferences.*

As Cycle 1 was a test cycle, the authentic participants had not made a commitment to carry out a full case study cycle. The other participants were not domain experts nor target stakeholders. Consequently, the particular outputs of the steps are not of significance as design challenges, briefs or wireframes. Rather, the key contribution of the activities reported here was to provide a safe environment in which project staff could experiment. Thus, the key outcomes in from the pilots are the valuable lessons learned

- **The methods.** These informed the design of activity structures in WP4.

- **Practical experience.** Work with pilot users provided a safe environment which enabled project teams to try out tools and to explore the challenges of addressing environmental dilemmas including interactions with very different policy stakeholders' needs and requirements.
- **Capacity building for GREAT partners.** While the partners have a wealth of relevant experience, the focus and context of the pilot activities were new. Partners are now prepared for more high-stakes activities with authentic policy stakeholders.

Nevertheless, although these were pilot activities, in some cases the work has generated initiatives that are being taken forward. This is the case for the work with Urban Gorillas (pilots 1.5, 2.4 and 3.3), which is proposed as the basis for a case study, and for pilot 3.1, which has informed in a less direct way a case study to be implemented in schools in Vienna.

Finally, the key lessons learned from the work reported in this deliverable are shown in the nine points below, with the implications for future WP2 work indicated in the associated bullet points.

1. All the designs that were piloted were effective in creating the desired outcomes: design challenges, design briefs and wireframes.
 - This experience has built capacity and activity designs that can be applied in forthcoming case studies with authentic stakeholders
2. Selected designs have been represented as activity designs in WP4, corresponding to steps 1, 2 and 3.
 - Formal representations of more complex activity designs are available for case study leaders
3. The combination of support tools used in the pilots was an effective support for collaboration and did not present problems for users.
 - *It is expected that most future WP2 work can be supported by*
 - email
 - Shared documents (e.g. Google Docs)
 - Video conferencing (e.g. Zoom, Google Meet and MS Teams)
 - Miro virtual whiteboard (or equivalent, e.g. FigJam, or LucidSpark).
 - Voting software (e.g. Mentimeter)
4. There is no single correct way to conduct a design activity, as the contexts and needs of problem owners vary greatly.

- In future work it will be essential to design processes for each case study, building on an expanding resource base of activity designs.
5. The possible contexts for interactions vary greatly, and a number of different designs were piloted for combinations of face-to-face and remote designs.
- WP2 should prepare for work with
 - All participants and facilitators face-to-face.
 - All participants in one location and all facilitators in another.
 - All participants and facilitators in separate locations.
6. Problem owners have differing degrees of clarity about the dilemma that they wish to explore before the start of the case study, creating a need to customise the activities in steps 1 and 2. This is shown in the contrast between the two pilots conducted with authentic uses. Die Grünen, in Frankfurt, were concerned to consult citizens on policy issues, but had no clear priorities, whereas Urban Gorillas in Cyprus were quickly able to decide on a dilemma and context without the need for a full workshop.
- It is to be expected that policy stakeholders will have widely differing orientations and priorities. This will have strong implications for WP2 activities, which may be very short or highly extended, depending on the policy stakeholder.
7. Work with authentic external users showed that the availability of key respondents is likely to be limited.
- There is a need to emphasise activity designs which achieve outcomes in a tight timeframe, and with a range of degrees of stakeholder input, from minimal to extensive. Possible approaches include preparatory interviews and data gathering by facilitators.
8. Project staff, professional politicians and policy-makers are compensated for their time, non-professional participants in design activities are not. This is a barrier to participation.
- If problem owners can provide some funding for participation of non-professional participants (if only out of pocket expenses) this could greatly enhance the quality of the insight reports which policy owners receive.
9. The plan of work foresees that GREAT staff will facilitate the wireframe design of a DiBL game and then pass this to WP3 for detailed technical implementation. Pilots of step 3 GREAT have suggested that case study facilitators can learn to use at least some aspects of the DiBL back end.

- In some circumstances non-technical staff or stakeholders could be more closely engaged in the development of dilemma games than had been anticipated, with support from SGI. This should be considered as an option in future case study cycles, as it offers a deeper collaboration in the game design process.

These lessons learned will be applied in the forthcoming case studies with authentic policy stakeholders.

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5. Compendium of WP2 activities and outcomes

Pilot 1.1. Step 1, Die Grünen, Frankfurt.

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i>	22/03/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Barbara Kieslinger
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://cloud.educs-hosting.net/s/6gSgN7GiKfsSgGQ?path=%2FWORK%20PACKAGES%2FWP2%2Fcycle%201%20reports%2FZSI%2Ffrankfurt_WS_22-March_2023
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1, Frankfurt
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 1, first workshop to explore local issues
<i>1.1.6 Language of the activity</i>	German

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

First exploration of the local situation; local issues that are “hot topics” that could lead to a dilemma game.

Aim to get input for:

- dilemmas requiring information on citizens preferences and attitudes
- the expected insights and evidence that can be offered to policy makers
- who should/could participate in the dilemma game

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

How to start a research cycle in a participatory way, following the GREAT Citizen Science research cycle. How to explore a specific local issue on climate change with a mixed group of representatives from a political party, who are active in local agenda setting

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

This was a pilot, thus the main research question for the case study was to identify whether there is interest from local policy makers in the game-based approach by GREAT for an improved dialog between citizens and policy makers

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

The meeting was set up by representatives from the political party “Die Grünen”, who have a strong environmental focus. All participants knew the person inviting them for the meeting personally; most were party members, and one was a student representative. All shared similar views on the importance of taking climate change measures. They participated as a favour to the person who invited them, but they were also genuinely interested in the GREAT project and the game-based approach.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

This was a pilot activity. There was a later follow-up workshop, but there is currently no clear indication that we will complete the full cycle with this group. Availability and timing are important aspects.

1.4 Design and Instruments

*1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.***

3 facilitators from ZSI

9 participants: 5 male, 4 female.
5 of the participants are official representatives from the Green party: 1 student (pupil) representative, 1 parent representative, 1 civil society representative, 1 person implementing participatory processes at local level working for a non-profit organisation.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Online workshop via Zoom.

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

As it was the first workshop we did not have any templates to use. We created a first structure of the workshop based on previous experiences.

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Miro board

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

2 hour session, following this structure:

Activity	Duration	Timing	Moderator
IMPORTANT: get consent to record the session and then get consent again so that it is recorded			
Start and introduction	10 Minutes	11:00 – 11:10	Barbara Kieslinger
Presentation of the GREAT project	15 Minutes	11:10 – 11:25	Barbara Kieslinger

Presentation of the objectives of the workshop	5 Minutes	11:25 – 11:30	Katharina Koller
Brainstorming of climate crisis related local topics	15 Minutes	11:30 – 11:45	Katharina Koller
grouping/clustering of the collected topics	5 Minutes	11:45 – 11:50	Katharina Koller
Voting on the topics	5 Minutes	11:50 – 11:55	Katharina Koller
Detailed discussion of most voted topic	30 Minutes	11:55 – 12:25	Barbara Kieslinger
Final feedback round	15 Minutes	12:25 – 12:40	Barbara Kieslinger
Next steps: Timeline, who wants to continue in the next steps of the research cycle	5 Minutes	12:40 – 12:45	Barbara Kieslinger

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

We plan to have a short feedback round at the end of the session with the following questions:

- What is your take-away from today’s workshop?
- What do you expect from a “gamified” approach to reach citizens?
- What do you expect from the GREAT project?

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

There were no deviations. We had to spend a bit more time at the beginning to explain to one participant the use of Miro, but all others were already familiar with the tool.

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The German language Miro board used in the activities is available here: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMfO6Lxs=/>. The main points may be summarised as follows. The brainstorming about the urgent topics related to climate policy brought forward the following issues:

- Traffic and mobility, priority for cycle lanes etc.
- Housing, how to make it affordable, how to continue building without using up all the green spaces
- Energy sources and how we deal with them
- Digitalisation and schools
- Specific issues about particular neighbourhoods.

The controversial topics were focused around how to better engage and communicate with people who have different expectations, and who do not know how politics and administration is done, and who don't get engaged until they are personally affected, and even if their own house is affected, they do not read the letters. The stakeholders wanted to know how to get better communication channels with people who are not engaged, marginalised people who do not have interest groups representing them, young people, parents, etc., to get better and more equal participation from different groups in society, with communication in both directions. A lot of participants feel there is a lack of information for citizens about what has been decided and implemented, and awareness of the processes. It was suggested that a quiz might help in raising awareness of how critical processes work, and how long it takes before a decision is taken and something is implemented. The team explained that this was what we wanted to do next, and that the issues could be transferred into dilemmas and role games. The stakeholders found the dilemma games interesting. The team explained that we would start with the dilemma game, and then move on to Playmob's quiz game. They asked who would like to continue with GREAT in the further steps of the game design, and four stakeholders agreed to an ongoing involvement. At the end of the discussion we were most focused on schools, as the student representative had some good suggestions of how to engage. One person also suggested that we should do a version in two or three languages, as there are many mother tongues in different areas of Frankfurt.

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

It was most important to first assess the overall interest in the GREAT idea and whether people would like to continue and with which topic. It was important to see who wanted to continue in the next steps and follow-up in a next workshop.

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

There was enough interest to continue, which led to a next workshop; however, timing was already a big issue; getting various people together for a follow-up was challenging.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The workshop methodology worked well overall. Most people had worked with Miro before except one older participant. We showed them how to navigate in Miro and how to add post-its.

We thought that we could discuss the top two ranked topics, but time did not allow for it.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

Timing is a major issue, as finding a time and date that works for everyone is really difficult, especially when it is coordinated from a distance. It would be better to organise it locally, e.g. connect it with events that the party has foreseen anyway and meet face2face.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

The activity was evaluated positively, the method worked well, However, time is very limited for these people, and they did not want to commit to time consuming activities. They already have a lot of experience in participatory democratic processes and have tested different formats to engagement with the local population

We posted the following questions:

Question	Post-its

<p>What can you take away from today’s workshop?</p>	<p>Impulses for information and participation in the context of the preparation of the climate protection plan “Climate Neutral Frankfurt 2035</p> <p>Interesting new approaches on how to make democracy / citizen participation more “user-friendly”</p> <p>New ideas and perspectives on public participation</p> <p>attention: we need to make sure that we include people at an early stage who do not come from our “bubble”</p>
<p>What do you expect from a “gamified” approach to citizens?</p>	<p>That citizens can playfully see what is possible (city level, legal framework etc.) and give informed feedback.</p> <p>Low-threshold</p> <p>Unconventional, addition entry into dialogue</p> <p>Involvement of FBAG/interest groups for people with disabilities</p> <p>Enables broad participation</p> <p>Inclusion & constructive, playful coming together of different parts of the population</p> <p>I hope that this will help to overcome resistance and break down prejudices.</p> <p>Informal learning about politics/ administration/ democratic structures</p> <p>More and wider participation</p> <p>Inclusive approach</p> <p>That more people, also from the “quieter” groups, feel addressed</p>
<p>What do you hope for from the GREAT project?</p>	<p>Exciting inputs that can be used for further work, also for urban participation formats.</p> <p>Rethinking participation processes with the media of the day, an opportunity for democracy</p> <p>Create opportunities for learning as well as participation</p> <p>More / other perspectives</p>

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

In the Frankfurt case we would have to think about giving people compensation for their time, e.g. the student representative would probably be willing to continue with the game-design and implementation, but we would need to offer them some compensation for their time. This would also generate greater commitment.

It is also important to consider that this group did not start with a dilemma they wanted to solve, rather, they agreed to participate because of personal contacts.

Pilot 1.2: Step 1, UNAL Colombia

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i> <i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	26/07/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Dai Griffiths, UNIR
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	Currently on UNIR Dropbox server
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activities
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 1
<i>1.1.6 Language of the activity</i>	Spanish

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

Documentation of an activity method that will shed light on an approach to carrying out step 1 of the GREAT case study cycle.

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

Establish if the first step in the GREAT Case Study Cycle can be carried out entirely online

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

What methods should be used in the cycle 2 case studies

Is Zoom, Jamboard and Mentimeter an effective combination of tools

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

This activity forms part of the test cycle, exploring the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches to the GREAT case study cycle. The test cycle can work with test users internal to the project, but a decision was made to work with participants from a different institution in another continent who had no background in the project.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

This is the first activity of two sessions which examine the first two steps in the case study cycle. The activities are split in two sessions, corresponding to T2.1 and T2.2 respectively. Each session is designed to be completed within a maximum of 2 hours. The participants are asked to imagine that they were asked to take the role of a political representative in the city of Medellin responsible for the environment, and to discuss the issues from that perspective.

1.4 Design and Instruments

*1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.***

The eight active participants came from the Department of Computer and Decision Science at Faculty of Mines, National University of Colombia (UNAL). Three participants were female. One was a research student, and the others were members of staff.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Online (Zoom)

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

Not applicable, as the template was not available when the activity took place

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Zoom <https://zoom.com>, Jamboard <https://jamboard.google.com/>, Mentimeter <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

Introduction (20 minutes)

- Introduction to the event
- Introductions by the UNIR team
- Introductions by the participants
- Presentation of the GREAT project by a UNIR team member
- Presentation of objectives for the session, role of participants and what is requested of them.
- Sharing links to tools in the chat and confirming access

Sub-activity 1: “Problems related to the climate crisis” (15 Minutes)

- Technical support: Jamboard
- Creation of post its
- Clarification of post its
- Discussion

Sub-activity 2: “Selection” (10 minutes)

- Technical support: Mentimeter
- Voting options to be read out and commented on, to ensure that all are understood by participants.

Sub-activity 3: “Measures to reduce or mitigate” (10 minutes)

- Technical support: Jamboard
- Creation of post its
- Clarification of post its
- Discussion

Sub-activity 4 “What information, and from whom?” (10 minutes)

- Creation of post-its
- Facilitator reviews contributions and invites clarification from participants

- Sub-activity 5 “How will the information be transmitted” (15 minutes)
- Technical support: Jamboard
- Creation of post its
- Clarification of post its
- Discussion

Link to the next session, focusing on dialog with citizens and introducing the technical resources of GREAT.

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

An evaluation form was prepared for distribution after the second of the two sessions.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

There was a problem with Mentimeter, described in section 2.3

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants’ responses to prompts, etc.

Sub-activity 1. Problems related to the climate crisis

23:30 Prompt: Which problems related to the climate crisis do you consider to be most urgent in your city? We are talking about climate crisis policies, but within that we need to focus on important themes which we can focus on. We’re not interested in general issues, such as high temperatures, or sea level rise, or food security. We need specific actions and measures that the city of Medellin could take, or is taking, to mitigate or combat the climate crisis. It’s also important that the issues could create interactions with citizens. So, for example, improving the monitoring of rainfall would not be of interest, because it does not involve a need for interaction with citizens. Please remember that this is a brainstorm,

so any idea is welcome at this stage. What do you think is the climate crisis issue which is most relevant for the city of Medellin. Think in local terms.

30:30 Clarification of Jamboard post-its, and discussion.

Sub-activity 2. Selection

40:00 Prompt: Of the problems identified in step 1, which do you consider to be the most urgent for your city? In your role as the environmental officials in the city of Medellin, you now need to decide which of all these topics that you have identified is the most relevant. It could be yours, or it could be someone else's. There is a link in the chat which will lead you to the issues that you have identified, and you need to give them a value on a Likert scale to indicate the ones which you think are most important. (The problems are read by the facilitator and understanding is confirmed). If you have any problems with the connection or finding the vote, please let us know. (On completion a screenshot of the Mentimeter outcome and a post-it of the most voted issue was placed on the Jamboard). Would you like to make a comment on this issue? (no response).

51:00 Prompt: We have a winner: desertification by cattle and agribusiness. It was democratically selected, but would the people who voted for it like to say something more about it, or the people who did not? (No response). So this issue has received the most votes. We would now like you to use green post-its to characterise the problem in three or four words, its causes. It could be lack of rainfall, or overexploitation, or pollution from agribusiness. But whatever it is, we need to know the characteristics of this problem in the city.

55:00 (Problems for facilitator with Jamboard in editing post-its, and participants see incorrect colours on their browser access to Jamboard. Facilitator stopped sharing, but the problem remained. Resolved after three minutes).

58:00 Now we need to follow a similar process. You have identified a clear problem. We would like to hear your comments on the post-its, and explanation of the problem.

64:00 Facilitator: Does this problem have an immediate impact on day-to-day life in the city?

Sub-activity 3 Measures to reduce or mitigate

68:00 Prompt: We know what the problem is, we have characterized it and explored its impact on citizens. Now we have to decide the most difficult part. On a blue post-it, please put measures and solutions that you as officials of the city could take to reduce or mitigate the impact of this situation? A new law, a new regulation? What would you do? We will give you a bit more time, because it needs some reflection. Every measure has a positive side and a negative side, and not everything is well received by society, or by industry, or by the farmers.

73:00 Review of post-its by facilitator. There are solutions here, but we need to think about specific measures. There are some mentions of education, and that is something that can be the basis of a policy, putting in place a new educational programme. There is a direct tax to regulate agricultural activity, that is certainly a political measure. Reforestation,

information campaigns, etc. (Facilitator groups the post-its, and with a colleague formulates options for a Mentimeter vote and shares the link. The voting options do not update in the participants' browsers.). No problem, we will do it in the old fashioned way. Facilitator asks each participant in turn which measure would be the most effective. (It becomes clear that the problem is that participants have not clicked 'submit').

78:00 Discussion of options and preferences led by a facilitator inviting each participant in turn and summarising.

87:00 Facilitator, two options have five votes each, but we need a winner. To make the next phase easier, I'm inclined to choose the tax. Is that acceptable? (no objections).

Sub-activity 4 "What information, and from whom?"

87:00 Prompt: You have convinced your colleagues in the city hall that you need to create a new tax on companies. You are going to implement it, and it will have an impact on the whole supply chain. To make the best policy decisions you need information. For example, think of the reaction against controls on car use. What information do you need to gather in order to design an effective policy?

92:00 creation of post-its

95:00 Facilitator reviews contributions and invites clarification from participants

97:30 Facilitator: We are running short of time, so I suggest we focus on how our voters will receive this measure, which will have an impact on the cost of meat, while improving the environment. How do the citizens see that balance? Do they understand the benefits?

Sub-activity 5 "How will the information be transmitted?"

99:00 Prompt: We would like to know how this measure will be accepted or not by the citizens. How will you interact with the citizens or businesses, etc. to get this information? The answers may identify channels which you know could be used, for example a survey in the street, or something more innovative.

101:30. Participants create post-its.

104:00 Facilitator summarises and discusses. Points out the need for two way communication, not just information delivery.

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

Input from the participants was gathered in the form of post-its on Jamboard, as shown in the screenshots below:

All the post-its on the same Jamboard

Figure 3-6: Jamboard outputs of pilot 1.2

The following boards were organised after the close of the session to clarify the content:

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The selected theme and scenario were carried forward to the second step in the methodology, which was addressed in another workshop with the same participants.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

This workshop was carried out entirely by means of videoconferencing, with participants who were not known to the facilitators. All the planned outputs were generated. Prior to the session the facilitators were concerned that there would not be sufficient opportunities to create confidence among online participants and to generate discussion. However, as can be seen from the following table, there was a substantial number of interventions by participants.

Gender	Requests for clarification	Contributions
M	1	9
F	7	8
M		4
F		4
M		3
M		2
F		2
M		2
M		2
Total	8	35

The videoconferencing support (Zoom) worked smoothly, and none of the participants had difficulties in working with the system.

Jamboard was an effective whiteboard system, although much more limited than subscription based alternatives.

Mentimeter worked well for the single step for which it was used, and could save time in the voting process. However, a technical issue prevented further use (see next section).

Please see the report on the second of the two workshops with the same participants for further reflections which apply to both workshops <Step 2. UNIR (UNAL Colombia)>.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

In sub-activity two the facilitator experienced problems with Jamboard in editing post-its, and participants saw incorrect colours on their browser access to Jamboard. The facilitator stopped screen sharing, but the problem remained. Resolved after three minutes.

In sub-activity three the facilitator grouped the post-its, while a colleague formulated the options for a Mentimeter vote and shared the link, but the voting options did not update in the participants' browsers. As an alternative the facilitator asked each participant in turn which measure would be the most effective. This was also done for subsequent votes. It later became clear after a time that the problem was that participants had not clicked 'submit' for the previous vote.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

Evaluation was planned for the end of Pilot 2.2.

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

None

Pilot 1.3: Step 1, UB internal pilot

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>6.3.1 Date(s) of activity</i> <i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	30/07/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Prof. Paul Hollins, UoB
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	None
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	The activity is a contribution to exploring a workshop method in the test cycle, and is designed to be potentially used in future cycles/case studies.
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	The activity is situated as an exploratory study situated in the 'Collaborate in Study Design' part of the research cycle.
<i>1.1.6 Language of the activity</i>	English

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

Whilst the activity may not directly contribute to a specific case study. This Pilot workshop will contribute to the development of effective workshop design for future activities.

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

The pilot study explores the use of a fast-paced, time limited learning design method, designed to establish effective methodologies to be applied with various user groups as the project progresses. The method can be used to establish priorities for question development, either self-generated or to explore previously developed themes.

1.2.3 Research questions.

a) What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

b) What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

The activity does not directly address an individual Case Study research question. Whilst using climate change priorities the contribution was primarily a pilot of a workshop design methodology.

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

This was an internal test activity carried out with University of Bolton students.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

Not applicable

1.4 Design and Instruments

1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.

Demographic : Masters Students in Computing at the University of Bolton, Ages between 22 and 39. There were 8 males and 10 females in the groups.

Group 1: 6 (Male x3, Female x3)

Group 2: 6 (Male x2 Female x 4)

Group 3: 6 (Male x3 Female x 3)

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

The location was an offline classroom setting in a university.

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

Not applicable, the activity was carried out before the templates were available.

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

A large interactive whiteboard was used together with a conventional flip chart to record the suggested priorities as these were identified. The boards were used throughout the sessions as feedback was received from each of the three groups. The board was used in a final plenary to discuss group findings to identify consistencies/inconsistencies and to discuss the data collected.

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

The agenda was an hour long and comprised

- Introduction, 10 minutes. Setting the scene and the objectives of the workshop.
- Individual Group Discussions around the short-term priorities as they perceived them for addressing climate change (3 minutes each, total 10 minutes).
- All group discussion (5 minutes) of the priorities identified and presented by each of the three groups.
- Steps 2 and 3 were repeated for medium term priorities (15 minutes).
- Steps 2 and 3 were repeated for long term priorities (15 minutes).
- A short plenary discussing the group outcomes and workshop (15 minutes /overran slightly)

Prompts: the initial discussion and presentation ten minutes and reflections in the plenary. This occurred at the beginning of the session,

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

An evaluation with Likert type scale questions is planned relating to the self evaluation of the session and learning outcomes from a student perspective.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

No divergence was necessary

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The participants were able to develop lists of priorities grouped into short/medium- and long-term priorities. (Some of these priorities overlapped whilst others were repeated. Priorities were categorised in terms of priority at different stages.

This corresponds to the first aspect of the design challenge, i.e.

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

The outcome was a list of priorities in climate categorised as short-, medium- and long-term challenges. How useful the outcomes are for case study development in terms of themes and content is debatable this given the group were not experts. The outputs could be used as relevant questions for targeted demographics.

Pilot Group 1			Pilot Group 2			Pilot Group 3			
	Short term	Medium term	Long term	Short term	Medium term	Long term	Short term	Medium term	Long term
High priority	CO2 Emissions	None	Population Control	Education	Plastic reduction	Government Sanctions	Information Communication	Information Cross Sectoral	Population Growth Control
	Renewable Energy	Re-Cycle	Waste Management	Renewable Energy	Go Green	Low Carbon Cities	Re Cycling	Government Policy	Reduce Heat Hubs
	Waste Management	(Re) Forestation	Robotics	(De) Forestation	Reduce Meat Consumption	Alternatives To Cars	Electric Vehicles	Alternative Energy	Reduce
Low priority	Forestation	Waste Initiatives	Recycle Initiative	Information Communication	(Re) Forestation	Robotics	Low Emissions	Remote Working	Create Smart Cities
	Reduce Car emissions	Waste To Energy	Government Policy	Waste Management	Sustainable Transport	Protect Ozone layer	Reduce Plastics	Re Cycling	Alternative Energies
		Audit and Management	Packaging	(Re) Forestation	Alternative Energy	Shield Earth From Heat	Government Policy	Re Forestation	Reduce Emissions

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The workshop was useful in piloting an approach to developing a set of priorities within a very short time frame.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The participants in the workshop were all very engaged in the process, and reflection on the subject seemed very important to them, the students were keen to experience the session. And contributed to developing the overall outcomes of the activity. The workshop was time limited and where this is a factor this could prove useful. The workshop was targeted at producing very specific outcomes and this was achieved.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

Getting participants focussed on the tasks was challenging as was managing three groups discussing the issues in one room. The group discussions required facilitation by an experienced facilitator to ensure all voices in the group were heard and the environment was conducive to open discussion.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

Two Likert scale questions were asked:

How much did you enjoy the process?				
Not at all	A Little	Medium	Good	Very much
0	0	1	4	14

How effective were the activities in leading to a good outcome?				
Very poor	Poor	Medium	Good outcome	Very good outcome
0	0	1	4	14

Thus the feedback was very positive: most enjoyed the workshop and thought it useful from their perspective.

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

None

Pilot 1.4: Step 1, DIPF internal pilot

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i> <i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	20/07/2023, 21/07/2023, 24/07/2023, 25/07/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Jane Yau, DIPF
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1w3Gr4yws9iAplx55RrvXYmyN9CjxnZDq
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activities
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 1, but the method could be applied to other steps.
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	English (Not in German)

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

The aim of this activity is for participants to agree on a single dilemma relating to climate change. The activity will be divided into two stages: first, an individual semi-structured interview activity with 5 (EduTech at DIPF) doctoral students (30 minutes), followed by a group activity with all of them to come to a joint group decision on a single dilemma.

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

To establish if a combination of face-to-face individual activities followed by a group activity can help to obtain the information we need from participants more rapidly.

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

<i>What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?</i>
Can the group of participants agree on a single dilemma with the highest priority? Does the use of individual interviews combined with a group activity constitute a quick and effective method for identifying dilemmas?

1.3 Background and Context

<i>1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).</i>
This was a pilot activity carried out with DIPF postgraduate students.

<i>1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.</i>
Not applicable, this was a one-off pilot activity.

1.4 Design and Instruments

<i>1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.</i>
The five participants were doctoral students at the educational technology group at the DIPF. The location of the individual interviews were via Zoom online and conducted remotely. One was female and four were male. They are colleagues at the same research group and work in the same research area, learning analytics. Hence, they know each other quite well.

<i>1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).</i>
The location of the individual activity was conducted online via zoom. The location of the group activity was conducted in a roundtable setting in one of the offices at the DIPF building in Frankfurt Am Main, Germany.

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

Not applicable. The templates had not been developed when the activity was carried out.

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

No specialised tools were used in the activity.

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

Stage 1.

Participants are briefed about the project and both stages of the activity beforehand. Each is also asked to sign a consent form (with an attached written project and activity briefing). (a situation in which a difficult choice has to be made between two or more alternatives, especially ones that are equally undesirable./a difficult situation or problem./an argument forcing an opponent to choose either of two unfavourable alternatives (logic)). The briefing gives the participants the chance (at least slightly) to prepare for the interview questions.

The interviews are recorded and transcribed completely for research purposes at a later stage. Brief notes are taken during the interviews, compiled in a table, and shared with all interviewees prior to the second stage.

The questions that will guide semi-structured interview are:

- Which problems related to climate change most worry you?
- Of these problems, which do you think is the most urgent to address in Frankfurt?
- What are the difficulties and challenges in addressing this problem?
- Can you express these difficulties and challenges as a dilemma?
- What information about citizens preferences and attitudes would help you to resolve this dilemma?

Stage 2.

The aim of the second stage is to agree on a single dilemma with the highest priority. The researcher facilitates the session, using the table of notes as a basis for the conversation, bearing in mind that it may be that no agreement can be reached.

The tables with the outcomes of the interviews are shared before the meeting.

Introduction and round of names and research area (five minutes)

In the group meeting, each participant shares why they think the theme in their table is important (3 minutes each= 18 minutes)

Group discussion about the most important theme that the participants would like to work on, followed by a consensus or a vote if necessary (35 minutes)

Break (15 minutes)

Identify

- What scenarios for the selected dilemma would be engaging for a game?
- Who would you need to work with to get information that would help you resolve the dilemma?
- What, specifically, would indicate the preferences and attitudes of the people you will be collecting data from?
- What information sources and content would people need to understand the selected dilemma?

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

At the end of stage 2, participants will be asked to fill in an evaluation form.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

There was no specific need to diverge from the plan for this activity. In the group face-to-face activity, one participant joined in virtually as he could not be present, and it worked out fine with the discussion and recording etc.

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants’ responses to prompts, etc.

All participants arrived at the online interview quite prepared. In particular, participant 4 had extensive knowledge on climate change, being a youth climate activist in the last years. Although participants 2 and 5 did not know the topic too well, they nevertheless had many worries and concerns and sufficient knowledge to provide a fruitful discussion. Participants 1 and 3 were aware of current climate problems and could elaborate on their answers to the interview questions. The five participants then joined together for the group discussion in stage 2 of the activity on 25 July.

Through the first stage of the study, with this group of participants, the five interview questions (sometimes with additional probing) made it possible for each participant to arrive at a single dilemma. A summary of participants’ responses is shown in the following table.

	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4	Participant 5
Most worried climate change problem(s)	Extreme weather affecting ecosystem, human & plants, mass extinction, emissions,	Extreme weather, diseases, Harmful chemicals used	Lack of biodiversity, water shortage, emissions	Water shortage, more govt investment needed, escalating problems e.g. violence	Rising temperatures (food, livestock, flood), Not enough forests, trees
Highest priority problem	Water shortage for agriculture	Food & chemical waste	Too many cars (electric)	Car-dependency	Rising temperatures
Difficulties in solving the problem	Communication of the topic is not at the right level	developing alternative non-harmful products, cannot force people to use certain products – higher costs	Electric cars are built but should rather advocate for public transport, non-independent politicians/industry	Convincing people to stop driving cars (boomers)	1) youth & elderly (e.g.) not educated to look after environment, 2) govts not prioritizing climate emergency
Citizens’ preferences and attitudes	1) Willingness to discuss, 2) topics open to, 3) age group, mindset flexibility	1)Spending habits	Income, age, cultural belief, mindset flexibility, if elderly can reach hospitals	Group they belong, what could convince them, their beliefs on car-dependency	Political ideas, what kind of mindset they have

Table 1. Summary of participants' answers from stage 1 of the activity.

All participants were able to describe a number of climate change problems that they were worried about, and subsequently narrowed these down to **one** climate change problem that they were most worried about. Similarly, they were able to pinpoint one problem that had the highest priority for them:

- Participant 1's highest priority problem was water shortage for agriculture.
- Participant 2's highest priority problem was food and chemical waste.
- Participant 3's highest priority problem was too many cars (including electric).
- Participant 4's highest priority problem was car-dependency.
- Participant 5's highest priority problem was rising temperatures.

Stage 2 of the activity took place face-to-face on 25 July. One out of the five participants connected via zoom (as he forgot that it was supposed to be a face-to-face meeting). Note that this did not affect the group discussion. This activity was recorded via zoom including the online participant and the 4 in-person participants (as the laptop camera pointed towards them for the recording during the activity). A summary of the notes in table form were sent to the participants the day before the activity took place (see table 1). The activity started with the participants each making a 2–3-minute pitch relating to why their particular theme is important. Then they were prompted to make a group discussion and try to agree on a single dilemma. Participant 1 suggested that since there were two participants whose theme concerned cars, this could be a good starting point, and the discussion was then centred around how cars could be reduced to protect the climate as well as challenges and problems associated with car-dependency. A possible solution would be to build car-independent cities with lots of infrastructure with public transport and facilities (such as supermarkets etc.), which would be reachable without the use of a car. All participants were very active and open-minded in the discussion, and were to an extent, easily agreeable as they shared similar views. Within an hour, the group had finished discussing issues around the five questions and provided detailed ideas, elaborations and answers. This was considered to be a successful outcome. The group of participants agreed that:

Car-dependency was the policy dilemma needed to be addressed

Families, young or single people, policy makers will be engaged in, and

Whether people or cities could be made less reliant on private car use and more on public or green transportation

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

Not applicable. This was a one-off pilot activity

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

Key takeaway – phase 1 of the activity was very successful in eliciting answers to the intended interview questions, even for participants with limited knowledge of the topic.

On reflection, part two of this activity may be much more difficult for a group of participants if they had very different views and were not prepared to agree with others.

Participants identified individual climate change dilemmas and reached a consensus on the highest-priority dilemma during the group activity.

The group discussion focused on various aspects of climate change, including the impact of car dependency on the environment. The participants engaged in a lively conversation, addressing issues such as the efficiency of electric transportation, the environmental consequences of lithium mining, and the challenges of transitioning away from car dependency. They discussed the feasibility of reducing car use, especially in cities designed primarily for cars, and the potential benefits of investing in alternative transportation infrastructure such as bikes and trams. Furthermore, participants explored ideas related to energy conservation, including wind parks and resource allocation.

After a robust discussion, the group reached a consensus on the policy dilemma that needed to be addressed: car dependency. They recognized the need to engage various stakeholders, including families, young individuals, and policy-makers, to transition towards more sustainable transportation options and reduce reliance on private cars.

The group discussion covered a wide range of climate change topics and showcased the participants' active engagement and open-mindedness. They explored potential solutions and expressed their concerns regarding car dependency and its environmental impact. Ultimately, the group agreed on the significance of addressing this dilemma to promote greener transportation alternatives.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The effectiveness of the interview questions and the facilitator's role were evident in both the individual interviews and the group discussion. The questions prompted participants to share their perspectives on climate change, fostering a productive and interactive dialogue. The facilitator played a crucial role in guiding the discussion and ensuring that it stayed on track.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

Occasionally, it required some steering by the interviewer in the right direction to get participants to express more precisely and to elaborate on their answers relevant to the interview questions. The way that the project brief was written was very helpful for them to prepare for the interview and in a short time (ca. 30 minutes) provide answers and a meaningful discussion. Participant 4, as a youth climate activist, would have liked to have known at which level (whether local, regional, national or international) the questions are targeting. In an updated future version of the project brief for pilot activities, it would be good to provide this information for the participants.

Participants provided valuable feedback, highlighting the positive aspects of the activity, including the effectiveness of exploring different perspectives and the importance of interactivity. Some participants suggested allocating more time for the group discussion, indicating a desire for deeper exploration of the topics. Additionally, there were suggestions to refine the clarity of certain terms, such as “issue” or “dilemma,” in the evaluation form. Participants also expressed that specifying the local policy level from the beginning would enhance clarity, especially for those with a global perspective.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants’ feedback on the activity.

Participants each filled in an evaluation form. The feedback included:

(Positive) Examples and seeing things from different perspectives of other participants help one to gain more ideas for elaboration. Enjoyed making the pitch.

(Positive) Participants were very open-minded. Interactivity and preparation of the discussion → not just brainstorming but with added necessary background information. The interviewer was also able to get the discussion going into the right direction. The brainstorming and the small debates given by participants were effective in producing good outcomes.

(Positive and can be further improved) One participant suggested that more time for the group activity would be beneficial as there could be many more aspects that could be discussed. Three participants would have liked to spend more time for discussion (including the youth climate activist).

(Can be improved) Words/questions were sometimes unclear – what is meant by issue or dilemma? On the evaluation form – the table where participants are asked to indicate the effectiveness of different aspects on a scale of 1 to 5 were perhaps not entirely relevant for this activity, or the aspects need to be rephrased so that the relevance of these different concerns relate more directly to the discussions of this activity. For the participant who was a youth climate activist, it was difficult for him to find a specific dilemma as he is already convinced of the problems and solutions on a global scale, and it was also difficult for him to focus on the local level. The local policy level could have been clearer from the start, and therefore, he was slightly confused during the stage 1 of the activity as he did not know the scope upfront.

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

This activity was very successful in eliciting answers to the intended interview questions, even for participants with limited knowledge of the topic. *This activity may be more difficult for a group of participants if they had very different views and were not prepared to agree with others.* However, due to the nature of the activity and the directness of the questions, it would also be possible within the same timeframe to determine if participants could not agree on a single dilemma. It was found that it was possible and feasible within a relatively short amount of time (30 minutes individual interviews participants to understand their single most worrying climate change concern), and then 1-hour group activity to get together and fairly quickly to agree on the single dilemma.

For the first part of the activity, the 5 questions are short and direct, participants were also given these beforehand and therefore had some time to prepare answers. However, the questions were straightforward for them, and they could provide their perspectives and opinions with ease. With moderation and redirecting, if the discussion went off-topic, the group activity was designed appropriately and could get participants to agree on a single dilemma.

This method requires little preparation time, which can be efficient and effective especially in low-resource situations. Using a small number of hand-written notes was sufficient to draw up the table which was then sent to the participants so that they can get an overview of the topics that are most worrying for the other participants.

In number 2 of the evaluation form, the questions were quite abstract and did not entirely relate to this research activity. The 9 aspects should be expanded and elaborated on to ensure clearer understanding for participants. Also, the question could be more precise – “please indicate how effective the activities were in **generating good outcomes(??)** for the following aspects”

Due to the size of the group being small (5 people), it was possible to achieve the activity’s objectives within the time allocated. If there were more participants, the time allocated may not be sufficient to allow each person to share their perspectives and views, in order to gain a group consensus.

Pilot 1.5: Step 1, Urban Gorillas

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i>	25/10/2023 – 26/10/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Anna Merry, FU <art.ma@frederick.ac.cy>
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1A5giEHmDucIs0qYRs8-OQMdedtmQJU3L
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activity: Urban Gorillas.
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 1
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	English / Greek

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

To identify a dilemma which can be the basis for a pilot activity.

To examine the potential for a full case study on this issue.

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

To explore how a GREAT case study can work with an organisation that has a clear pre-existing environmental mission.

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

This was a Cycle 1 activity, piloting the approaches to be used in GREAT. The objectives were therefore to contribute to case study protocol, and the activities which it contains.

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

The work was carried out in collaboration with Urban Gorillas (<https://urbangorillas.org/>), who are a multi-disciplinary team of creative urbanites united by their common vision and enthusiasm for constantly improving life in cities. Their team works to transform public spaces into lively, innovative and inclusive hubs, to cultivate civil society and to impact policies. The organisation shares expertise in arts and architecture, urban design and planning, landscape design, environmental engineering, economics, communications, cultural project management, as well as a commitment to innovation. Since 2013, Urban Gorillas have been active in city-making through urban regeneration, community engagement, and the implementation of socio-cultural and artistic projects in public spaces.

Using diverse tools, they aspire to transform urban spaces into creative public environments through the dynamics of public interactions. Urban Gorillas work with citizens, artists, schools, business, universities, NGOs and municipalities, adopting non-formal education practices and creative tools to transform urban places into sustainable hubs, offering human-centred solutions for urban design and planning which are backed up by research, design workshops, and community engagement.

The work of Urban Gorillas has been financed by the European Commission, the Ministry of Education and Culture in Cyprus, municipalities and various embassies across Cyprus.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

This was the first activity in a small scale cycle 1 with an authentic user group. It is not foreseen to be a full case study, but rather an exploration of the potential for a full case study in a future cycle.

1.4 Design and Instruments

1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.

The participants were:

Anna Merry (Frederick University)
 Veronika Antoniou, Founding Member and Board Director (Urban Gorillas)

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

The activity was carried out remotely

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

No template was used.

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

None

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

The activity was planned for three stages

- Briefing about GREAT and exchanges on the possibilities for collaboration
- Brainstorm of possible dilemmas
- Selection of a design challenge

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

None

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

None

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The activity consisted of two phone meetings of one hour each, a Frederick University staff member and a board member of Urban Gorillas.

The first meeting presented the GREAT project and Urban Gorillas and explored the potential for collaboration.

The second meeting discussed possible themes which could serve as the basis of a dilemma game.

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

The discussion consisted of relevant dilemmas which were appropriate to UG as well as suitable pilot studies for GREAT. Initially the conversation centred around the 15-minute city concept and the issues currently facing Cyprus in relation to travel and moving towards sustainable movement in the city as this was a suggestion by Frederick University based on current research. During the conversation UG brought up the issue of repurposing rooftops as a way to provide multiple spaces in the City.

The following dilemmas were brought forward:

- Use of alternate vehicles
- Upgrading the park and ride schemes
- Incentives for alternative methods of travel
- Urban planning upgrades, greening and improvements
- Use of public/large buildings roof spaces as social spaces
- Greening of multiple private owned buildings roof spaces
- Water management/collection on private owned buildings roof spaces

Three options were selected for further consideration, all of which were related to roof spaces.

- Use of public/large buildings roof spaces as social spaces
- Greening of multiple private owned buildings roof spaces
- Water management/collection on private owned buildings roof spaces

Follow up discussions after the meeting led to Urban Gorillas committing to the design of a DiBL game.

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

A very short activity was sufficient to develop the outline of a design challenge, and the experience showed that this is a viable approach for a GREAT case study. However, the nature of the sponsor makes this a special case:

- The sponsor already has a clear idea about the kinds of interventions which they would like to make
- It is credible that the sponsor (a) has reached consensus on these ideas within the organisation and (b) is conducting their own consultation activities with the citizens that they are working with.
- In other circumstances such an abbreviated approach would not be justifiable

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

Detailed conversations between individuals with decision making capacity.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

None

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

None

<i>2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).</i>
None

Pilot 2.1: Step 2, Die Grünen, Frankfurt

Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i> <i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	21/06/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Claudia Magdalena Fabian
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://cloud.educs-hosting.net/s/LSCXzjoMqng7Zko?dir=undefined&path=%2FWORK%20PACKAGES%2Fcycle%201%20meetings%2Ffrankfurt_WS_21_June_2023&openfile=1676222
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1, Frankfurt
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 2; recap of previous workshop and presentation of dilemma and Playmob game
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	German

1-2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1) Outcomes: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

Aim of the workshop was:

- Recap of the previous workshop by ZSI (22. March 2023) and validation of the findings
- presentation of the dilemma game (DIBL) with small activities; ZSI and SGI created a dilemma game to demonstrate the functionalities
- Presentation of Playmob-game (Playmob) with small activities
- Reflection, how the game-based approach could be applied for future real-life cases to get more concrete ideas for the cycle 2 implementation

1;2.2) Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

Presenting the results from the 1st workshop to the participants and collecting first feedback regarding the “dilemma game” and “Playmob game”. After the demonstration and testing of the games, the participants should get an impression of how the GREAT games could be used for real-life cases. With this input, the research team hoped to obtain more concrete ideas for further real-life cases (cycle 2)

2.3) Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)

This was an internal pilot. The main objective was to get a first reaction and feedback for the GREAT games.

To validate the results from the first workshop and collect further feedback regarding the GREAT games (dilemma & Playmob)

Dilemma game: ZSI and SGI designed an example to present the main functionalities and the application and to collect first feedback regarding the Playmob game

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

The 2nd workshop was a ZOOM online-workshop. For the workshop-setting, the research team used ppt for the presentation of the recap and the GREAT games (dilemma game and play mob game); the main discussion points were documented on the Miro board

Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1bPI-bes5UUaLVHn7ViiK3s8tkdo3GnprEzPArUNdM4w/edit?pli=1#slide=id.g23b4baebdb6_0_127

Miro-Board: https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMfO6Lxs=?share_link_id=55020156807

Detailed transcript: https://cloud.educs-hosting.net/s/LSCXzjoMqng7Zko?dir=undefined&path=%2FWORK%20PACKAGES%2Fcycle%201%20meetings%2Ffrankfurt_WS_21_June_2023&openfile=1676222

Participants were representatives from the political party “Die Grünen” with a strong environmental focus; in addition the ZSI research core team (BK, KK, CF), one representative from SGI and two from Playmob, and the GREAT project coordination (JY) were present.

The participants from “Die Grünen” knew each other.

3.2) Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

Most of the participants are party members, while one of them is a student representative; they all shared the same view, that new approaches could be used to tackle the climate change and challenges; they were in general quite interested in the project, but since all of them were lacking availability and time no further concrete ideas for real-life implementations (cycle 2) were made.

In general, the workshop also provided the game-provider like DIBL and Playmob first insights, how future users may react to the GREAT games.

1.4 Design and Instruments

4.1) Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.**

6 facilitators from ZSI

6 facilitators from Playmob

1 facilitator from SGI

1 project coordinator from DIPF

1 female participant from the Green Party in Frankfurt City Council (Stadtverordnete) with focus on mobility

1 female participant from the Green Party in Frankfurt City Council (Stadtverordnete) with focus on education and schools

1 male participant, who is a Student Representative

1 male participant from the Green Party in Frankfurt City Council (Stadtverordnete) with focus on housing and youth

4.2) Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Online workshop via Zoom (tools: ppt and Miro board)

4.3) Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used in the activity, and any additional instruments or templates which you designed. Provide links.

A template was used (presentation of ppt, testing of tools and documentation of Miro board)

4.4) Identify the tools that are used in the activity. Provide links if available.

PowerPoint presentation and Miro board

4.5) Describe how you structured the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines you used for structuring the activity.

A two hour session; following this structure:

Activity	Duration	Timing	Moderator
IMPORTANT: get content to record the session and then get consent again so that it is recorded			
Start and introduction	10 Minutes	09:00 – 09:10	Barbara
Recap of previous workshop & workshop goals	20 Minutes	09:11 – 09:30	Katharina
DIBL presentation and approach	15 Minutes	09:31 – 09:45	Simon
Playmob presentation and approach	15 Minutes	09:46 – 10:00	Jude and Joost
Showing and testing the Playmob game	15 Minutes	10:01 – 10:15	Jude
Showing and testing the DIBL game	15 Minutes	10:16 – 10:30	Simon

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

As the timing for the workshop was very restricted there was no formative evaluation of the event itself; the participants were already used to the Miro board and the online setting; at the end participants are asked to add to the Miro board their questions regarding the further possible steps in implementing the GREAT methodology in their context and whether they had any further questions regarding the two game-based approaches. The questions are to be collected on the same Miro board as the one used for the first workshop.

Reporting

5) Participant contributions and outputs

5.1) Based on notes taken during the activity or transcripts, report on the contents of the activity, i.e. participants' inputs, their responses to prompts, materials they developed, etc.

After the introduction and testing of the GREAT games, following general implementation scenarios were discussed with the participants. The German language Miro board created during the activity is available here: <https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMfO6Lxs=/>. The outcomes may be summarised as follows.

- Currently different social media tools are used by the political parties; still unclear, how to best use the “games” to improve the dialogue with citizens and policy makers.
- Possible implementation areas are mobility & transport or green spaces with the inclusion of images.
- Topic should not only be discussed in Frankfurt but also in other places.
- The games should be included in active participation processes.
- A close cooperation with the respective department (Dezernat) is recommended, especially with the dilemma game.
- According to the participants, the game-approach could really include more people in the participation process.
- It is recommended, to use the game-approach not only for those, who are “directly” affected, but to give the public a platform to share their opinions with others.
- The implementation of the games is highly dependent on the specific process and applied scenario. Example: use events, where the public could share their opinions – the games-approach could reach out to other target groups.
- Dilemma game is useful for discussing for instance mobility issues and “afterwards” the Playmob game (quiz-game) could be spread to the broader public.
- Other possible implementation areas are “how citizen participation could be fostered”.

5.2) Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What information provided by participants will be used in the following steps?

The main conclusion of the workshop was that the participants will look out for further possibilities to implement a real-case scenario in Frankfurt, since they now know how the GREAT games look like and what kind of functionalities they have. Unfortunately, all of them have only limited availability and time and it seems that the 'design' and implementation of the games should not be underestimated.

5.3) What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The main conclusion of the ZSI-research team was that in order to implement a real-life scenario for cycle 2, the GREAT team needs to find (a) policy makers with an urgent need for game-based approaches (dilemma game) and (b) a wide network to spread it in the wider community (Playmob).

Besides, policy makers have only limited time and availability but could maybe get further support if there is additional funding for additional staff and resources.

6) Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

6.1) What worked well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

Since it was the 2nd workshop, the participants did not only know each other, but also the main research team. The ppt presentation gave a good overview of the games and test activities added a playful aspect.

6.2) What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

It was quite difficult to find a date for the 2nd workshop.

6.3) Describe participants' feedback on the activity, and evaluation carried out (if any).

The participants showed interest in the presented games and did evaluate the workshop in general quite positively. However, since time is always limited no commitments for further activities were agreed.

The suggestions on the Miro board gave us some more insights into what participants understood from the presentations and where there were still doubts. In the suggestions regarding possible implementation scenarios we also learned that the participants see a number of good implementation scenarios for both approaches, they value the approach and affirm that new insights can be gained for policy makers; they related the approaches to their previous experiences and made a few suggestions for improvements, such as adding more images and reducing the text in either of the two approaches.

Figure 7: Participant feedback pilot 2.1

6.4) Provide further reflections or observations (if any)

As said in the protocol of the 1st workshop, the GREAT research team should consider giving people some kind of compensation for their time and contributions.

In addition, the participants had no real need for any of the proposed activities; they participated because of a personnel invitation.

Pilot 2.2: Step 2, UNAL, Colombia

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i>	02/08/2023
<i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	Dai Griffiths
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Pending
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	Cycle 1 pilots
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Step 2
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Spanish

1.2 Objectives and research questions

<i>1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?</i>
Documentation of an activity method that will shed light on an approach to carrying out step 2 of the GREAT case study cycle.

<i>1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?</i>
Establish if the second step in the GREAT Case Study Cycle can be carried out entirely online

<i>1.2.3 Research questions.</i>
<i>a) What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?</i>
<i>b) What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?</i>
What methods should be used in the cycle 2 case studies? Is Zoom plus Jamboard an effective combination of tools?

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

This activity forms part of the test cycle, exploring the strengths and weaknesses of different approaches to the GREAT case study cycle. The test cycle can work with pilot users internal to the project, but a decision was made to work with participants from a different institution in another continent who had no background in the project.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

This is the second activity of two sessions which examine the first two steps in the case study cycle. The activities are split in two sessions, corresponding to T2.1 and T2.2 respectively. Each session is designed to be completed within a maximum of 2 hours. The participants are asked to imagine that they were asked to take the role of a political representative in the city of Medellin responsible for the environment, and to discuss the issues from that perspective.

1.4 Design and Instruments

1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.

The eight active participants came from the Department of Computer and Decision Science at Faculty of Mines, National University of Colombia (UNAL). Five participants were male and three were female. One participant was a PhD student, and all others were members of staff.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Online (Zoom)

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

Not applicable, as the template was not available when the activity took place

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Zoom <https://zoom.com>; Jamboard <https://jamboard.google.com/>

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

Introduction (5 minutes)

Sub-activity 1: Identification of a scenario (15 minutes)

- Create post-its
- Clarify post-its and group into similar topics
- Selection of scenario theme (the largest group of post-its)

Sub-activity 2: identification of a measure or decision (15 minutes)

- Create post-its
- Review and discuss post-its.
- Voting: Select one measure.

Sub-activity 3: Scenario definition (20 minutes)

- Facilitated discussion, facilitator to take notes on Jamboard.
- Voting: select on scenario.

Sub-activity 4: Who should participate in the game (15 minutes)

- Create post-its
- Review and discuss post-its.
- Voting: Select one measure.
- Compile and agree results

Evaluation (5 minutes)

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

An evaluation instrument has been prepared and is available here:
<https://forms.gle/cJgnjfk9ykz9Do78>

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

The participants were pressed for time, and were unable to stay to complete the evaluation form at the end of the session. They said that they would complete the evaluation as quickly as possible, but in fact only one form was submitted.

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

Introduction.

00:00 This session will be similar to last week, with the same shared board although we will try to keep it a bit shorter, as two hours is a long time online. This week we will be asking you to make a still greater imaginative effort than last week. Please ask us for clarification whenever you need to.

Sub-activity 1: Identification of a scenario

04:00 Prompt: We have identified a theme, the impact of intensive industry on the climate and the city. What we need from this session is a scenario, a description, which could be the basis for the design of a game, more specific information on the situation. It is not entirely clear to us what the relation is between the problem you have chosen and the climate crisis. There clearly is a relationship, but even without the climate crisis, the problems of intensive agriculture would still exist. So the first question is "What is the most significant effect or impact caused by intensive arable and cattle farming in relation to the climate crisis?" (the question is pre-loaded onto Jamboard).

07:00 Not all participants had access, resolved by the facilitator.

10:00 review grouping and summary of post-its. Four groups of impacts, discussion of how they relate to climate change. Output summarises most frequent similar post-its: "Loss of natural habitat, creating deforestation, and in this way increasing concentration of greenhouse gasses".

Sub-activity 2: identification of a measure or decision

18:00 Prompt: The game which we will be designing will be based on the exploration of a difficult decision. We commented last week on the dilemma of the regulation of traffic in city centres. There is a conflict of interests between the health of citizens and the impact on

convenience and economic interests. Here we need to think of a measure that the government could take which would generate a conflict of interests. So it is not enough to suggest more research. “Can you identify a measure or political decision in the area of intensive farming, which implies a conflict of positive and negative consequences?”

23:00 create posts-its

28:00 review and discussion of post-its. Only four post-its. Facilitators elicit the groups impacted (positively and negatively). Who would be in favour and against? (A facilitator also provided a post-it and discussed it).

39:00 selection of one measure. Facilitator asked each participant in turn for their opinion.

Output: “Tax on the carbon footprint of cattle farming and tax benefits for reforestation”

Sub-activity 3: Scenario definition

41:00 Prompt. This step is maybe the most interesting and the most difficult. Because what we want to achieve now is a description of a scenario that is sufficiently specific to be the basis for the design of a game. We also need to think of the roles which should be included. This time we will simply have a conversation, and Joaquín will take notes in Jamboard, it’s too complicated to put on a post-it. An example which doesn’t have much to do with deforestation: imagine electricity generation policy. The situation could be a city that generates electricity using coal from local mines. The town hall decides to make a big investment in solar panels and windmills. This situation is useful, because there is a conflict of interest between the miners and other social groups, as well as other possible uses for the invested funds. The roles could include a miner, the director of the power station, an official of the miners’ union, the director of a school next to the power station, a representative of the neighbours’ association, etc., and of course the town hall. They are people and entities that are involved in the situation. So that’s the kind of thing we are looking for, material for a conflict resolution game, what they call in English a ‘serious game’. A role playing game in which the players work on an imaginary scenario, where they have to resolve the kinds of problems we are describing. It is like a dramatization of the situation. What is the scenery, and what are the roles. Imagine a TV or theatre drama, where they introduce this kind of tax. What kind of situations arise between the characters? On Jamboard: “Please propose specific situations within the problem which could be the basis for a conflict resolution game. Which roles should be included in the selected situation?”

47:00 proposals from participants. The first was a more elaborated version of a measure. The facilitator asked for more details on the roles, which were provided.

58:00 Facilitator clarifies the nature of a serious game.

60:00 Conversation continues

69:00 There has been a proposal for an ‘escape room’ game, facilitators ask what the roles would be.

72:00 Facilitator asks, “Where could we situate this idea?”

73:30. Facilitator asks for votes.

Output: “Industry and the consumer: packaging, incentivising the user of ecological packaging. The consumer is oriented to choosing ecological packaging.” (Decided at random from two equally voted options)

Sub-activity 4: Who should participate in the game

76:30 Prompt: For this step we’ll go back to the procedure from before, that you put your post-its on the board. So we have an idea for a game, but who do we want to play this game, to obtain the information we need. Groups of people, social profiles, institutions, etc. We are not talking about fictional players. On the Jamboard: “Once a game has been created based on the scenario that you have defined, who should play it, to generate the information that you want?”.

78:30 Facilitator requests more specific roles within the packaging industry.

80:00 Post made, and facilitator asks for comments, or disagreements, none forthcoming.

82:00 Thanks

83:00 Evaluation form request

86:30 Close

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

Input from the participants was gathered in the form of post-its on Jamboard, as shown in the screenshots below:

¿Cuál es el efecto o impacto más relevante causado por la agricultura y la ganadería intensiva en relación a la crisis climática? **1**

The screenshot shows a Jamboard with the following sticky notes:

- Agotamiento del recurso hídrico, sobre consumos energéticos y la emisión no controlada de emisiones de gases efecto invernadero**
- Emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero**
- Disminución en la productividad de los suelos**
- deterioro de la capacidad de los terrenos para los cultivos con impacto en los costos de la comida**
- Aumento de desechos producto de la producción agro industrial, tanto en el proceso de producción como en los productos finales.**
- Perdida del hábitat natural, que crea deforestación, aumentando de esta manera las concentraciones de gases de efecto invernadero.**
- reducción de bosques con impacto en calid aire**
- reducción y contaminación de agua**
- Pérdida de hábitats naturales**
- tala de arboles para la adaptación de tierras**
- Deforestación**

Figure 8-10: Jamboard outputs of pilot 2.2

¿Podría identificar una medida o decisión política, en el entorno de la agricultura y ganadería intensiva, que implique un conflicto de consecuencias positivas y negativas? **2**

The screenshot shows a Jamboard with the following sticky notes:

- Perdida del hábitat natural, que crea deforestación, aumentando de esta manera las concentraciones de gases de efecto invernadero.**
- Creación de de zonas de protección natural estrictas, como parques nacionales, donde este limitado la actividad agropecuaria y el acceso de los ciudadanos**
- impuesto en relación a la huella de carbono de la producción agropecuaria & beneficios tributarios por reforestación**
- Establecer un tope de tala por terreno ej. por cada cierto metros cuadrados de terreno solo se puede talar hasta cierta cantidad de vegetación. Limitar aprovechamiento de terreno**
- Exigir certificación de ganadería sostenible con implicaciones fiscales y legales en caso de no cumplirse**

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The time was very short for carrying out all the necessary activities. But campaigners, politicians, etc. will have still less time available. Finding creative solutions to make effective use of limited time with stakeholders will be one of the key success factors for the GREAT cycles. It is proposed to add preparatory activities to identify policies or proposed policies that require information. These could involve one-to-one interviews, perhaps with junior personnel from stakeholder organisations.

In this pilot, we chose a strongly directed method, and this proved effective in generating the required outcomes and articulating the process. Indeed more direction might increase effectiveness still further. However, the high degree of direction also constrains the spontaneity of dialogue. Moreover, it remains to be seen how stakeholders with a high degree of public or social responsibility will respond to a highly directed process. Consequently, the ground rules for the meetings will need to be agreed with participants at the beginning of each case study.

An obvious difference between this pilot and activities in future cycles is that the pilot participants identify an issue which concerned them. This is not a good starting point for a case study, and leads to inconsequential discussion and confusion. It is proposed that it should be a condition for the identification of a case study that there is a pre-existing dilemma that creates a need for information. It would be a high risk strategy to hope that such a dilemma will emerge. This requires focused work by the team organising pilots.

The participants deviated from the selected theme in session 2, step 3 (formulation of a scenario). It is expected that this would not happen in an environment where the focus was on a real dilemma. The three facilitators agreed that in future iterations

- The interaction between administrators and administered, or between governed and governors, should be stressed still more strongly at the beginning of the session.
- The metaphor of a drama or TV series episode helped the participants to understand what was being asked of them in creating a scenario. This was a piece of improvised guidance during the session, but should be incorporated as a resource for facilitators.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

This workshop was carried out entirely by means of videoconferencing, with participants who were not known to the facilitators. All the planned outputs were generated. Prior to the sessions the facilitators were concerned that there would not be sufficient opportunities to create confidence among online participants and to generate discussion. However, as can be seen from the following table, there was a substantial number of interventions by participants.

Table 2: Pilot 2.3, summary of interactions

	Session1 (129 minutes)		Session 2 (87 minutes)	
Gender	Requests for clarification	Contributions	Requests for clarification	Contributions
M	1	9	1	7
F	7	8		
M		4		5
F		4		6
M		3		
M		2		
F		2		4
M		2		3
M		2		
Total	8	35	1	25

The rate of interactions was almost exactly the same in the two sessions (25 interventions in 87 minutes is equivalent to 34.5 interventions in 120 minutes). However, in the second session the average contributions per participant was 5, as opposed to 3.9 in the first session, Moreover, the

contributions tended to be longer; the design of the scenario in session two had the longest contribution (four contributions with an average of 3:48 minutes each).

From this table we conclude that

The online process was able to support sufficient interaction, leading to the generation of the required outputs.

Despite four participants dropping out (including one of the principal contributors from session 1) participation was maintained throughout the two sessions, and indeed gathered momentum.

Technical support

The videoconferencing support (Zoom) worked smoothly, and none of the participants had difficulties in working with the system.

Jamboard was an effective whiteboard system. Following issues identified in the previous pilot (Pilot 1.2), It was much easier to use with a separate board being created for each step, with the output of the previous board added to the first post on the next.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

It was harder than expected to explain to participants what they needed to do. The facilitation team agreed that

The interaction between administrators and administered, or between governed and governors, should be stressed still more strongly at the beginning of the session.

The metaphor of a drama or TV series episode helped the participants to understand what was being asked of them in creating a scenario. This was a piece of improvised guidance during the session, but should be incorporated as a resource for facilitators.

Conversation tended to be dominated by a small number of participants. This was hard to correct online, although it was less the case in the smaller group for session 2. Future designs should set out to avoid this, perhaps through the use of break-out activities, or through collaboration with facilitators who know the participants and can make targeted interventions to include them all.

Jamboard was an effective tool, but it is possible that the use of post-its took the place of dialogue. It would be a high risk strategy to organise an online workshop without this type of support, but this trade-off should be borne in mind when designing future sessions.

There was a satisfactory degree of interaction between participants and the facilitator, but an almost complete absence of horizontal interactions between participants. Consequently the sessions took on something of the nature of a taught class, with participants responding to prompts. This may not occur in an authentic environment in future cycles, but it is a design criteria which should be addressed. In response to the lack of horizontal discussion, the facilitators found that they were speaking more than they had planned to, providing reflections which could more effectively have come from the participants (e.g. session 2, steps 1 and 2).

The highest level of participation was in the design of the scenarios. However, the development of DIBL games based on the ideas which were generated would not be straightforward. Participants tended to think in terms of games that they were familiar with (console games, escape room, etc.). This is a challenge for the design of the cycle methodology.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

As stated above, the participants were pressed for time, and were unable to stay to complete the evaluation form at the end of the session. They said that they would complete the evaluation as quickly as possible, but in fact only one form was submitted.

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

None

Pilot 2.3: Step 2, internal design pilot

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity</i> <i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	15/09/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Tim Garder, SGI, tim@seriousgames.net
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1gb9hlg-PjU8J_KYxYDZ_XbKYf14vBOG4
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activity
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 3
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

To pilot an approach to step 2 of the GREAT research cycle, and raise capacity in the project team.

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

To establish a method whereby a design brief for a DiBL game can be created.

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

- Is this workshop framework structure an effective route to collaboration on a design brief?
- Is the design template an effective tool for collaboration on a design brief.

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

This workshop took place in the second of three training sessions provided by SGI for project partners. The first session consisted of an introduction to the DiBL platform, while the present session involved conceiving a design that would provide the basis for a dilemma game. It is often assumed that a dilemma simply has two sides, and that the challenge is limited to which one to take. But a dilemma can be much richer than this, and it is positioned in a brief or framework. When they start designing a dilemma, they don't have a clear idea of what they want to examine, what outcomes they want, how they want to tell the story. This workshop raises capacity in the project, and establish a practical design method. It is an ambition within GREAT to develop this method so that it is both more encompassing and more rigorous.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

Not applicable

1.4 Design and Instruments

*1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.***

One participant from each of the five academic partners in GREAT (one partner had two representatives). Four females and two male.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Online

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

None, but the worksheet used is a candidate for inclusion as an activity design in the GREAT case study protocol.

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Zoom, Miro

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

The workshop used the following worksheet, adapted from worksheets used previously by SGI. The version used in the workshop had boxes for written input.

Conceiving the design. The participants work in small teams, completing a worksheet with the following questions, and discussing their design solutions. They then create wireframes in Miro.

Metanarrative

- Narrator's perspective
 - What suits your participants best? (1st, 2nd or 3rd person)?
 - e.g.: 1st person: I am in Poland, 2nd person: You are in Poland, 3rd person: Peter is in Poland
- Short or branching narrative?
 - If several different branches of the story are desired, telling different sub-stories according to the participants' choice. Should the narrative be short and straightforward or more complex and branching?
- Deep involvement of the participants?
 - What degree of "immersiveness" is desired for the participants (depends on the narrator's perspective. Should the participants be personally involved in the story? Feel on their own body how the theme unfolds. e.g. through role-playing by the teacher, roles or unexpected external events.
- Fictional or 1:1 with reality?
 - Home environment or abroad?
 - Should the story be a real story, or should the story be fictional? Should the story take place in your home country or somewhere else, e.g. Poland?

Blended learning or only digital?

- Should the solution only take place in the virtual world, or should there be other elements, such as physical objects? It can be props (e.g. cards, game board, checkers), actors (e.g. actor), roles (e.g. authorities, groups) or events (e.g. an arrest or action). Draw

out knowledge/behaviour in the classroom or do physical things in the classroom that influence choices digitally. Facilitators, participants and externals can, for example, have different roles.

Narrative options

- *Dilemmas*
 - Which dilemma-filled situations should the story contain, that the participants must decide on?
- *Different endings*
 - Should there be an opportunity to let participants determine the final outcome of their actions?
- *Knowledge and/or behaviour*
 - Should the story provide knowledge?
 - Should the story create reflection?
 - Should the story change behaviour?
 - Should the story create calls to action?

Social options

- *Cooperation and/or competition*
 - Create collaboration between students and create space for knowledge sharing and reflection or pit students against each other.
- *Anonymity*
 - Can participants vote anonymously on their own devices?
- *Individual performance or team effort*
 - Should the individual student fight his own case/opinion, or should there be a team effort? Should the teams cooperate or compete against each other?

Technical options

- *One or more answer options*
 - Should participants be able to choose only one answer each time they are asked to choose, or should students be able to choose multiple answers (can be combined)?
- *Share ideas with everyone*
 - Should participants have the opportunity to share their thoughts with the facilitator and/or other participants?
- *Voting on the best idea/thought/solution etc.*
 - The participants choose the best ideas etc. and use them in DiBL.
- *Point system/variables*
 - Scoring of unique and meaningful variables can be linked to all choices and to the learning objectives. Can be used as a competition element or to keep track of students' choices and progression. Can be used to "lock" ways up with and actively through the story.

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

A separate evaluation session was scheduled on Zoom after the end of the three workshops, see report on activity 3.2.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

None

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The participants were highly engaged and worked without difficulty with the worksheet and the Miro board. They experienced a steep learning curve on how to make a good dilemma, but were very productive. The outputs of the workshop, and subsequent work on pilots by FU and ZSI demonstrate that they are competent to know what constitutes a dilemma and what is possible within the technical framework, and to think through how we can get people to engage with the themes we want.

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

The participants agreed that it's not easy to design a good dilemma that actually gets people discussing what you want them to discuss in a way that you want them to discuss it. This will need to be a strong focus in future case studies.

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The worksheet framework and Miro are an effective combination in designing dilemmas.
In future workshops a slightly larger group might be better, to help keep the interactions flowing.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The combination of the worksheet framework for dilemma generation and a Miro board.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

Shortage of time.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

See report on activity 3.2

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

Pilot 2.4: Step 2, Cyprus Urban Gorillas

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity. DD/MM/YYYY</i>	15/11/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym & email.</i>	Anna Merry, FU <art.ma@frederick.ac.cy>
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1A5giEHmDucIs0qYRs8-OQMdedtmQJU3L
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activity: Urban Gorillas
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 2
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	English / Greek

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

- To make a final choice of dilemma
- To identify the stakeholders involved in the dilemma
- To generate ideas for a game narrative
- To gather input on the current state of the dilemma and relevant materials which could support game development

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

To explore how a GREAT case study can work with an organisation that has a clear pre-existing environmental mission in defining the requirements for a dilemma game.

1.2.3 Research questions.

a) *What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?*

b) *What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?*

This was a Cycle 1 activity, piloting the approaches to be used in GREAT. The objectives were therefore to contribute to case study protocol, and the activities which it contains.

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

See report on Cycle 1, Step 1, FU-Urban Gorillas.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

A list of candidate dilemmas had been prepared in the previous meeting, for Step 1, and following the meeting agreement to participate in the design of a DiBL game was obtained.

1.4 Design and Instruments

*1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.***

The participants were:

- Anna Merry (Frederick University)
- Veronika Antoniou, Founding Member and Board Director (Urban Gorillas)
- Marina Kyriakou Project Manager and Board Director (Urban Gorillas)

Marina Kyriakou, Architect and Urban Planner, was invited as an expert on the subject of rooftop spaces, the theme identified in Step 1, at which the other two participants were present.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Zoom meeting

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

No template was used.

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Google drive shared documents, DiBL

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

The activity discussed each of the objectives in 1.2.1 above in turn. Given the small number of participants, no structure was needed for the meeting.

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

None

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

None

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The interactions consisted of an hour of conversation between the three participants.

The outcomes were recorded in Google Docs.

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1K12lzcVzNYI9DmYWG72oxY7y2jV4PWc/edit#heading=h.gjdgxs>

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

Urban Gorillas (UG) explained that they have previously been involved in ECRN (European Creative Rooftop Network). ECRN is a network of organisations, working 'together apart' to use European rooftops as creatively as possible, exploring the future use of this partially undiscovered layer of urban space. ECRN creates international connections to maximise local impact.

The main content of the meeting was:

- UG identification of a policy action/dilemma related to the Climate Emergency which they would like to test amongst a specific group, and explanation of the reasons why this policy action/dilemma was chosen.
- UGs introduced the concept of rooftops and the projects they have been doing so far
- UG described how the use of rooftops can be related to climate change and how the repurposing of rooftops can work towards climate neutrality
- Discussion of the specific policy relating to rooftops or the overall concepts that we would like to (and can) test amongst groups of participants
- Who the groups of participants should be (citizens/building owners etc)
- What could usefully be done with the results
- Discussion of desired outcomes for UG.

During the activity the participants had access to DiBL. Towards the end of the meeting it was decided that the specific issue to concentrate on in relation to the general theme of rooftops should be the greening of privately multi-owned rooftops and the incentives that could be offered to citizens. Although greening of the rooftops is directly linked to the climate emergency there are also additional benefits to the action.

The shared document on Google Drive recorded:

- Lists of Incentives for rooftop repurposing
- A list of resources to support policy development
- List of Good Practices and Case Studies

- Identification of Barriers to Rooftop usage

Multiple potential groups were identified for participation in the DiBL game

- Homeowners
- Building Developers
- Management companies
- Architects
- People who rent accommodation
- Neighbours
- Potential buyers

An important issue moving forward with the DiBL pilot is to finalise the choice of participants.

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The outputs created the foundations for the design of a DiBL game, to be carried out in Step 3.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The practical activities with a DiBL game were valuable so that UG could fully understand how the Game would work.

Working with experts in the target field, who had already thought deeply about the dimensions of their chosen dilemma, meant that fast progress could be made with a small group.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

None

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

None

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

None

Pilot 3.1: Step 3, Die Grünen, Frankfurt / Vienna

1. Planning

1.1 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity DD/MM/YYYY</i>	15/06/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Barbara Kieslinger, ZSI, kieslinger@zsi.at
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMEI6jrM=/ https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVND5iPI4=/ /
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Pilot case of Cycle 1, Frankfurt and Vienna
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 3
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	German and English

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

- To build on the outputs of the Frankfurt pilot activities in the creation of wireframes for a DiBL game
- To prepare for a future Vienna case study

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

To explore how easy or difficult it is for someone inexperienced to design a dilemma game, based on an initial input of themes and priorities.

1.2.3 Research questions.

a) What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

b) What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

The main research questions concerned evaluation and impact assessment

- How can we set up a DiBL game in a way that offers us the possibility to get data for our evaluation and impact?
- How can we set up a game to get information that our stakeholders would like to get?

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

The activity was carried out by 3 ZSI team members who are also all involved in the GREAT project and who also ran the workshops with the Frankfurt group; Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen from Serious Games was added to the activity at a later stage.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

The Frankfurt pilot case study provided the information needed for a design brief in step 2. After this the respondents were not available for further activities and the process came to a halt. In parallel, the ZSI team had the ambition to design a dilemma game, based on a real dilemma in Vienna, which addressed a similar issue to the one discussed in the Frankfurt case. This activity therefore combined the ambition, firstly, to make use of the outcomes already achieved in Frankfurt, which would otherwise have remained unused, and secondly to prepare for a possible future case study in Vienna.

1.4 Design and Instruments

*1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.***

The activity initially involved only internal ZSI participants Katharina Koller, Claudia Fabian, and Barbara Kieslinger.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

The workshop was online, using a Miro board.

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

No specific template was used

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Miro Board

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

Only a small number of people were involved, so the activity was unstructured, with focus provided by the objectives and materials available. The duration lasted approximately 2 hours in total.

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

We did not do any evaluation; if this activity is done with external stakeholders I think it would be good to ask feedback afterwards. This would not be with a large number of people and thus a short feedback round might be the most appropriate evaluation.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

The three participants from ZSI originally planned to design the game on their own. However, it proved quite difficult to start thinking in a game logic, and although a main dilemma was identified it was a challenge to turn it into a game with various options and trigger peoples opinions. Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen from Serious Games International was contacted once the team were stuck with the game design and they talked him through the storyline. He then made a draft design for the game and then we discussed it again and made some additional changes together with him.

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

There was simply a discussion of the design as it evolved.

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

This activity was a first attempt to design a DIBL game, based on the input received from the workshops in Steps 1 and 2, exploring how easy or difficult it would be for someone inexperienced to co-design a dilemma game.

We learned that:

It is not a simple task to transfer a question or dilemma into a serious game logic. It is a real challenge to involve people in this activity who are not experienced in game design, and it also takes some time to learn the logic of DIBL. It was really important to get the help from a professional to transfer the story into a coherent dilemma game. We suggest that co-design activities with stakeholders should only be carried out with a very limited number of people. An alternative approach would be to make a first draft, based on the input from the stakeholders and then present it to them and get their further input and feedback to modify the game accordingly.

It became clear that it is important to establish where and how we can get data for our impact assessment once the game is implemented. This has to be thought through from the very beginning, e.g. will players have discussions in a face to face setting and can we document that? How is the game implemented in a purely online setting? And how can we split up the groups into breakout rooms? How engaging is the whole game and how do we phrase the question to make sure we get answers that are relevant for the policy stakeholders? Do we rather let the plays take on certain roles (role play) or do we want them to voice their own opinions directly?

The game will not be used as it is, but it provided a good insight into how such DIBL games can be designed.

These lessons learned will be valuable in developing the Vienna case study, as will the template that was created by SGI.

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

As said above, co-creation of a serious dilemma game needs professional support and we would not include a large number of participants to the co-design; it should be in a rather small group

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

Generally Miro works quite well for this type of activity. A few design templates from DIBL would be very useful; so whenever someone plans such an activity they would already have a set of templates they could choose from and adapt the game according to their specific context and needs.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

It is difficult to get into the game’s logic. It is also difficult to assess how long a game would take, maybe this comes with experience.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants’ feedback on the activity.

No evaluation was done

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

Pilot 3.2: Step 3, Internal design pilot

1. Planning

1.2 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity DD/MM/YYYY</i>	19/09/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Tim Garder, SGI, tim@seriousgames.net
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1gb9hlg-PjU8J_KYxYDZ_XbKYfl4vBOG4
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activity
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 3
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	English

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

- To pilot an approach to step 3 of the GREAT research cycle
- To raise capacity in the project team.

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

- To establish a method whereby case study facilitators can create wireframes with stakeholders
- To explore the opportunities for non-experts to collaborate in the creation of dilemma games directly on the DiBL platform.

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

- Is this workshop framework structure an effective route to collaborative wireframe design?
- To what extent can case study facilitators create draft games directly on the DiBL platform?

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

This pilot involved sessions in both the second and third in a series of three workshops organised by partner SGI to raise capacity in the consortium. In the second part of the second workshop, the participants worked with the dilemmas specifications that they had developed with a worksheet and represented them as wireframes in Miro. In the third workshop the participants worked directly on the DiBL platform to produce draft games based on these wireframes.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

Not applicable

1.4 Design and Instruments

*1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). **Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.***

One participant from each of the five academic partners in GREAT (one partner had two representatives). Four female and two male.

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Online

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

None

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Zoom, Miro, DiBL platform

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

Workshop 2: Participants work in small teams to transfer their dilemma descriptions to Miro, and present their outputs to other teams.

Workshop 3: SGI describes the technical aspects of the DiBL platform, and the elements that can be used. The facilitator then makes a small dilemma game which the participants can play. The participants take their ideas from Workshop 2, and experiment with translating them into an actual system, presenting their results and discussing them.

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

A separate evaluation session was scheduled on Zoom after the end of the three workshops. A Miro board was prepared with sections for 'stop', 'start', and 'continue' for the participants to add post-its to.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

None

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The participants created wireframes on the basis of their dilemma descriptions developed in the first part of workshop 2 (see below). The participants also succeeded in making short draft dilemmas games in the tenant on the DiBL server. These were not finished games, but they were playable. Then they presented their dilemma to the other groups, and all participants played them.

Deliverable 2.1

Figure 13: Miro wireframes from pilot 3.2

Figure 14: Screenshot of draft DiBL implementation

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

The participants agreed that it's not easy to design a good dilemma that actually gets people discussing what you want them to discuss in a way that you want them to discuss it. This will need to be a strong focus in future case studies.

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The evaluation and the experience of working with the participants suggests two possible roles for GREAT case study facilitators.

- GREAT staff facilitate the wireframe design of a DiBL game on Miro (or something similar), and then pass that over to SGI for detailed technical implementation.
- GREAT case study facilitators can learn to use the DiBL back end, and create dilemma games themselves. It appears daunting at first, but the participants were very effective. In the evaluation session they said they enjoyed the technical work, designing the pages and linking to questions.

It is suggested that each university partner should have access to a DiBL tenant which they can experiment with, with SGI support where necessary.

These findings suggest that the boundary between Step 3 (wireframes) and Step 4 (implementation) may be more flexible than had been assumed.

In future workshops a slightly larger group might be better, to help keep the interactions flowing. More time should be allocated for work with the DiBL platform. Participants were keen to continue, but only managed to complete one step into the dilemma. This precluded branching, which is tricky and involves key design decisions: When they should make a choice? What happens with that choice afterwards? What dilemmas?

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The hands-on activities with the DiBL backend were accessible and engaging for the participants.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

Shortage of time.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants' feedback on the activity.

The participants posted the following points to the evaluation Miro board, in a separate session following the completion of all three workshops.

Stop: practices we can say bye to: None

Practices we should start

- Consider functionality for more different purposes - e.g. is it a DiBL for researching something (like in GREAT), only for learning. these purposes might come with different requirements for DIBL
- Consider how we frame the case to give the right outcome
- Include a survey/questionnaire functionality (e.g. for baseline evaluations)
- Consider having a visual map like a Miro board that you can view at the same time as the DiBL is being made to visualize the connections between pages rather than having to preview
- Consider more engaging visualisations of responses - e.g. word clouds for free text responses. similar to functionality in Mentimeter.
- Allow teams to be formed during a game, or maybe the possibility to switch teams.

Practices we should carry on doing

- Providing feedback on real-life situation
- Giving immediate and contextual feedback
- Very user friendly backend
- Easy to use authoring system
- Feedback can also be scaffolded
- Allow users to play the games more than once
- Good for collaborating and interacting with others concerning important topics
- Good learning resource / tool
- Allow users to make deeper reflections
- Branching is a great aspect of DIBL
- Provide alternative choices and outcomes
- Continue providing a simple and attractive interface for the participants so as not to encourage and bias opinions.

Actions:

- Consider templates for specific use cases of DIBL
- Consider an additional view visualising the DIBL flow
- Consider functionality to validate the flow (e.g., checking for dead branches)
- Consider & implement new visualisations for (free text) responses
- Graphics & video

Questions

- Matrix participant questions
- How can we implement a participant pre-survey in DIBL? (Note from facilitator: This request is not really for a full survey, more a question of gathering opinions. In GREAT you may want some citizens to provide their input and opinions, and others to deal with the resulting dilemmas in some way.)
- Consider how it looks like on mobile, improving response rates
- How can we come up with new teams' functionality without promoting competition?

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

Pilot 3.3, Step 3, Cyprus Urban Gorillas

1. Planning

1.3 Please situate the activity

<i>1.1.1 Date(s) of activity DD/MM/YYYY</i>	17/11/2023
<i>1.1.2 Contact person name, partner acronym and email.</i>	Anna Merry, FU <art.ma@frederick.ac.cy>
<i>1.1.3 Link to the materials of the activity</i>	https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1A5giEHmDucIs0qYRs8-OQMdedtmQJU3L
<i>1.1.4 Case study of which this activity is a part</i>	Cycle 1 pilot activity: Urban Gorillas
<i>1.1.5 Step in the cycle to which the workshop contributed</i>	Step 3
<i>1.1.6 Language(s) of the activity</i>	English

1.2 Objectives and research questions

1.2.1 Case study objectives: What are the intended results of the activity that will move forward the case study?

To create a wireframe for a DiBL game

1.2.2 Research objectives: What will be learned about the case study methodology?

To examine how a GREAT case study facilitator can take on a consulting role in the creation of a DiBL game, i.e. that the sponsors provide input, but the facilitation team does the hands-on design work.

1.2.3 Research questions.

What are the overarching research questions for this case study which this activity contributes to?

What are the specific research questions for this activity (if any)?

- What are the likely responses of stakeholders for an initiative promoting the greening of privately multi owned rooftops?
- What incentives would be effective in promoting an initiative for the greening of privately multi owned rooftops?

1.3 Background and Context

1.3.1 Describe the environment and social context of the activity (if this is provided elsewhere, please provide a link).

See report on Pilot 1.5.

1.3.2 Describe the dynamics and progress of the case study which the activity is part of.

The dilemma and the outline for the game had been identified in activities with two of the leading participants in Urban Gorillas (UG) in Cyprus (<https://urbangorillas.org/>). The dilemma game design was created by the pilot coordinator, and a member of the SGI technical team, who acted in what may be termed a ‘consulting’ role, in the sense that they had gathered requirements from the UG team, and then took responsibility for the design.

1.4 Design and Instruments

1.4.1 Please describe the participants and relevant characteristics (e.g., gender, age, professional background). Do not include personal data you are not allowed to share.

Anna Merry, Frederick University

Tim Garder, Serious Games International

1.4.2 Describe the location and setting of the activity (including online/offline).

Zoom

1.4.3 Identify the template from the GREAT case study cycle guidance that was used to design the activity. Describe any additional instruments or templates which you designed, with links.

None

1.4.4 Identify the tools to be used in the activity. Provide links if available.

Zoom, Miro, DiBL

1.4.5 Describe how you plan to structure the activity, including the length of the sections, the questions, prompts, or guidelines for structuring the activity.

The activity is focused on the creation of a design for a dilemma game. It consists of a dialogue between the pilot facilitator (who has developed a good understanding of the dilemma and the objectives of the sponsor, and also has a good understanding of the DiBL platform) and a member of the SGI team (who can guide the facilitator through the detail of the design process, and provide guidance on effective designs).

1.5 Evaluation

1.5.1 Do you plan to carry out an evaluation for this specific activity? If so, what type of evaluation will you do, what is its goal? Please include the instrument in the materials (see 1.1.3).

None. A meeting has been held with ZSI to plan for evaluation of the DiBL activity when it is carried out with participants in Step 4.

2. Reporting

2.1 Adaptation of the plan

2.1.1 Was there a need to diverge from the plan for this activity at any point? What changes were made and why?

None

2.2 Participant contributions and outputs

2.2.1 Describe the interactions during the activity. You can refer to notes taken during the activity, transcripts, participants' responses to prompts, etc.

The interactions were focused on the task of creating a design, and were documented in the wireframes that were generated (see below).

2.2.2 Summarise the main outcomes relevant for the GREAT case study cycle. What decisions or information provided by participants will be used in the following steps? Indicate what documents were generated during the activity, with links.

For the DiBL game a minimum of 8 participants will be necessary, with a maximum of 50. We will decide based on if we will run the DiBL online or face to face. An option was to work with current apartment owners and to ask questions about how they would feel about using the roofs and gain instinctive feedback. We could then introduce the concept of an incentive, and give them roles. Potential topics for the role play included:

One person lives on the top floor, but another lives on the ground floor that already has a private garden: should the incentives be the same?

Should access be allowed for all residents, even if they don't agree with the initiative? Would a tax reduction be an effective measure?

etc.

The SGI representative stressed the need to find ludic activities, so that the activity does not become simply a matter of "Well if you give me money I will do it".

The practical decisions taken were:

- target groups for a pilot – Apartment owners or Developers (the construction company who build and sell)

- Issues for the developer: If it costs the developer money they won't want to do it - need to raise the price of the sqm - The solution has to benefit but green building has a higher cost
- We should concentrate the pilot on new buildings
- Not to introduce climate change too early in the DiBL. When climate change is mentioned it distracts from the main focus for the participant – in response be sure to add the other benefits of rooftop design. e.g. The social aspects
- Some discussed questions/dilemmas/incentives: who has access - how do you want to do this - you are in the dilemma - how do you solve it - You are in teams - put them in apartments - discuss - ask the developer - you are building the roof terrace - how do you make the offer and what do you want in return? - what would be the best approach? - Then show the ideas - these are suggestions of the municipality, what reimbursements wouldn't you like. e.g. should it be for all, you didn't want to be part of it. what is most fair
- Advocated strongly to have a role play aspect for example, types of owners – family – single – older couple etc. As well as who live in which location of the building,
- To add a questionnaire at the end - now we have discussed the dilemma - do you have other ideas?

POLICY EXPLORATION SECTION: By the year 2050, all European countries have the goal of being climate neutral. Unfortunately Cyprus is behind in many aspects required to achieve this goal. In addition our Green spaces of the City are one of the lowest in Europe. Utilising roof spaces is a practical method that has proved to be successful in other EU countries.

As your building manager we have gathered you here to discuss a new policy which the government is considering implementing. The policy is that every apartment building will have to create a common green space roof space (25% coverage) which will also act as a social space.

- Possible issues:**
- Higher Priced Apartments (Cost to the Developer)
 - Who will Maintain the Gardens?
 - Who can use the Gardens?
 - The penthouse may lose its personal roof garden
 - Risk of damp to apartment below

ROLE PLAY SECTION
It is difficult to be objective when you are already living a specific role within a building. Lets do a role play exercise to see the arguments from various perspectives.

Figure 15: Miro wireframe from pilot 3.3

2.2.3 What are the implications of these contributions and outputs for the design of future activities in this case study?

The wireframes that were produced provide a basis for moving ahead with a DiBL activity for stakeholders.

2.3 Reflections on Implementation and Methodology

2.3.1 What worked particularly well? (e.g., questions and prompts, specific tools, role of facilitator, ...)

The fact that the facilitator of the pilot had completed training in DiBL had greatly helped in the gathering of relevant information, and also meant that the development of the wireframes proceeded rapidly. The expert advice from the SGI staff member was invaluable in guiding the game design strategy.

2.3.2 What difficulties, challenges or issues did you encounter?

As documented in 2.3.1 the prior knowledge of the facilitator significantly aided the production of the wireframe, as well as the expert advice and collaboration from the SGI. Yet the biggest challenge during the design of the game was recognising the DiBL platform as separate from a traditional workshop, and how to essentially build ‘fun’ into the game. This is where the expert advice and experience from SGI was invaluable. The first version was reworked significantly to overcome this challenge. i.e. careful rewording of questions, and the addition of the roleplay. Additionally, the facilitator and SGI expert spent significant time to take the issue of where the notion of climate change should be introduced. This was seen as a challenge as from experience in such games holding the interest of players is key to success. It is crucial to keep the rooftops subject at the forefront rather than the overall issue of climate change as to keep the game to the focus of the specific policy.

2.3.3 Describe the results of the evaluation and include any participants’ feedback on the activity.

None

2.3.4 Further reflections or observations (if any).

None

